

**Visualization and Analysis
of Genealogy in
*Tārīkh al-Ṭabarī***

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Disclaimer

Just before handing in this thesis, my attention was brought to the book of Peter Webb, *Imagining the Arabs*. It discusses some of the topics mentioned here and offers updated insights into some topics for which I have used older sources. Due to the circumstances, I was only able to briefly address his work in paragraph 4.4 but I think it would have been very interesting and fruitful to have engaged more with his work. By now, I have read the book completely and I'm working on a more complete comparison of Webb's results with those of mine. It's completion, however, will have to wait until a later date.

Summary

Al-Ṭabarī, an early Muslim multidisciplinary scholar from Baghdad, describes in his work *Tārīkh al-Rusul wa-l-Mulūk* (The History of Messengers and Kings) the history from the first human Ādam to up until his own time (304 AH/916 CE). While describing the history, Ṭabarī and his sources pay great attention to providing genealogical information. This current research examines the function and significance of this genealogical information within the work itself and for its author, Ṭabarī. Limiting its scope to the period between Ādam and Muḥammad, the information will be processed into a family tree and then analyzed on the basis of two elements: time and space. This research will show that the genealogy Ṭabarī provides is mostly internally consistent, that the genealogy largely supports the work's chronology, and that the genealogical information might have had a link with land tax in Ṭabarī's present.

Introduction

In many societies over time, a person's lineage played an important role socially and religiously. If someone has a parentage that is considered 'good', he/she often receives a better social position including certain privileges while a 'bad' lineage might result in a lower social position. This is also the case for ancient Middle-Eastern societies. Ancestry played an important role in social, religious, and political standing in pre-Islamic and Islamic times. According to Franz Rosenthal, the Arabs living in this area made written or oral collections of genealogies: the so-called '*Ansāb*' works. These genealogies linked groups and individuals together into tribes.¹ Tribes were very important in this area because they allowed for cooperation between individuals and families in an area where provisions were often scarce. Additionally, being a member of a tribe offered protection to individuals against others.

After the Prophet Muḥammad² had completed his mission in the early seventh century the importance of genealogies changed. If a person could prove that his ancestors belonged to the family of the Prophet, the tribe of the Prophet (the Quraysh), or one of the early companions of the Prophet, he/she was given certain rights. Rosenthal references in this regard the example of the founding of the *dīwān*-system

¹ Franz Rosenthal, 'Nasab,' in *Encyclopaedia of Islam Second Edition*, edited by P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs, P.J. Bearman, et al, Leiden: Brill, published 1998, accessed online February 6, 2023, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_SIM_5807.

² All Arabic names in this Thesis are rendered in transcribed form using the English transcription method.

by the second caliph of the ‘Umar ibn al-Khaṭṭāb [r.13-26/634-644]³. The *dīwān* is a register containing the names of the Prophet's relatives, his tribe, and important companions of the Prophet. The individuals included in this register were entitled to an annual allowance or part of the loot captured during the early expansion of the Islamic Empire. Later generations could also claim these benefits and so it became important for the administration to record and canonize the lineages, although a complete consensus seems not to have been reached at any point in time.⁴

In the course of time, the actions of ancestors or an individual began to play a more important role in determining social status than genealogy. A lineage that could be traced back to a relative or early supporter of the Prophet was no longer sufficient to get a high social rank. The genealogies were thus increasingly decorated with traditions (*akhbār*) that recorded the lives of peoples' ancestors. For new Muslims, who did not come from the same region where the Prophet had lived, it now became possible to gain a higher prestige by performing good (religious) deeds. The recording of context of lineages eventually ensured that the genealogies became embedded in historiography.⁵ Only a few historical works from the early Islamic period have survived to the present day. One of these works is by the scholar Abū Ja‘far Muḥammad ibn Jarīr al-Ṭabarī [d. 310/922].

Ṭabarī was primarily a jurist with his own Islamic law school (*madhhab*⁶) in Baghdad, the capital of the Abbasid Caliphate.⁷ Ṭabarī was a very prolific academic and wrote several works in a number of scientific disciplines. He made a 24-volume Quranic exegesis (*Jāmi‘ al-Bayān ‘an Ta’wīl āyat al-Qur’ān*), wrote several book collections on Islamic law (*Ikhtilāf al-Fuqahā‘*, *Kitāb al-Laṭīf*), compiled a few small books on theology (*Al-Tabṣīr fī Ma‘ālim al-Dīn*, *Ṣarīḥ al-Sunna*), began at the end of his life a large collection of traditions (*Tahdhīb al-Athār*), and compiled a ten-volume work of

³ The first number in square brackets is the Islamic era (*hijri*), the second number is the Common Era (CE). The year 1 Hijri corresponds to 622 CE. The Islamic calendar is based on the moon. Instead of the sun. A lunar year is 10 or 11 days shorter than a solar year, so the difference of 622 years is getting smaller as years pass.

In this thesis, years are placed in square brackets so that they are easily distinguishable from the reference numbers that will be introduced in Chapter 2.

⁴ Rosenthal, ‘Nasab.’

⁵ Rosenthal, ‘Nasab.’

⁶ *Madhhab* means law school in a legal context. The term can also be translated or interpreted differently, as will become clear later in Paragraph 2.2.

⁷ The Abbasid Caliphate [750-1258 CE] covered most of the Middle East, Persia up to the Amu Darya, parts of North Africa and Eastern Anatolia. The Abbasids came to power after they rebelled against the Umayyad Dynasty [661-750 CE], the dynasty that had taken over the empire that Muḥammad and the first caliphs had founded.

history (*Tārīkh al-Rusul wa-l-Mulūk*) in which he described the history from the creation of the earth to his own time.⁸ He enjoyed considerable prestige as a jurist in his time, but today he is best known for his Quranic exegesis and historical work. What makes his historical work *Tārīkh al-Rusul wa-l-Mulūk* ('The History of Messengers and Kings', hereafter simply *Tārīkh*) stand out is that it has been (nearly) fully preserved and contains a lot of information of which the original source has been lost. Many scholars who wrote about early Islamic history after Ṭabarī therefore made direct or indirect use of material originating from *Tārīkh*.⁹

In line with the described development of the embedding of genealogies in historiography, *Tārīkh* is full of names and lineages. These lineages do not form some sort of clear structure, however. Therefore it is difficult to understand who is descended from whom and how the different individuals relate to each other. This confusion is, among other reasons, caused by the sheer amount of lineages mentioned and the fact that they are scattered throughout the text. Yet the attention Ṭabarī paid to these lineages makes it seem as if genealogy had a certain importance to him. This thesis will therefore focus on this genealogical information and what function it served. This will be done by first creating a family tree that contains all the lineages mentioned in *Tārīkh*, and then analyze this family tree using the historical-critical method. Due to the limited scope of this study, only the first part of *Tārīkh* will be examined.

The first part of *Tārīkh*, as I have limited it, describes the history of Ādam up to the Prophet Muḥammad and includes the creation of the earth, the creation of man, the Flood, the Israelite history, the Persian¹⁰ history, the Persian kings and the Arab history. Sometimes this period is called the "pre-Islamic period" because it chronologically precedes the mission of the Prophet Muḥammad. For this study, this term is not suitable as for Ṭabarī Islam was also present before the time of the Prophet

⁸ This is just a selection of the books he wrote. Most of the works mentioned above are (partly) available today. Biographical information and information about the works that Ṭabarī wrote can be found in the work of Yāqūt al-Ḥamawī [d. 627/1229]. Yāqūt al-Ḥamawī, *Muʿjam al-Udabāʾ*, Al-Maktaba al-Shamela, accessed online October 7, 2022, 6:2441-69, <https://shamela.ws/book/9788/2438>. An extensive English biography was written by Rosenthal. This biography largely corresponds to the content of the work of Yāqūt: Franz Rosenthal, *The History of al-Ṭabarī: General Introduction and From the Creation to the Flood* (New York: Suny Press, 1989), 5-134.

⁹ Rosenthal, *General introduction*, 136.

¹⁰ In this thesis the term "Persian" is used to refer to the traditions associated with Zoroastrianism. Ṭabarī makes frequent use of these traditions, but it is difficult to distinguish between Zoroastrian information and information from other traditions from the same geographical area without specialized knowledge. That is why I have decided to use the general term 'Persian'.

Muḥammad. A more accurate name for the period in line with Ṭabarī's view would probably be 'the pre-Prophet Muḥammad period'. However, this name is not very common and may cause confusion. To avoid confusion, the period is referred to in this study as 'from Ādam to the prophet Muḥammad'. This corresponds roughly to the period from Ādam to about 600 CE.

In concrete terms, this research will answer the following question: *What was the function of the genealogical information, mentioned in the period from Ādam to Muḥammad, in the historical work Tārīkh al-Rusul wa-l-Mulūk within the text itself and its author, Ṭabarī?* To answer this question, a family tree will first be created based on lineages mentioned in *Tārīkh*. This will help to get a better overview and understanding of genealogical information itself. This is followed by an analysis of this family tree on the basis of the historical-critical approach. Specifically, this means that the genealogical information will be studied in the context of the information in the text and in Ṭabarī's own context. The first will be achieved by taking into account the information from the stories in which the genealogical information is found and by comparing the chronology of the events in the text with the genealogy. Ṭabarī's own context is taken into account by linking Ṭabarī's professional and political circumstances with the genealogical information in the analysis.

The analysis of the family tree in chapters 3 & 4 will be based on two elements that play a central role in *Tārīkh*: time and space. Time plays an important role in the organization of history and genealogical information because the family tree consists of generations. The second element, space, has a prominent role since almost all events in *Tārīkh* contain a description of the physical setting and the individuals in the family tree also lived in certain areas. The Arabic text of *Tārīkh* will be the basis for the family tree and its analysis. The part of the ten-volume Arabic version of *Tārīkh* that I used ranges from volume one to volume two page 176. In order to make the family tree accessible to non-Arabic readers, reference will also be made to the 38-volume English translation of *Tārīkh*.¹¹

¹¹ In this thesis I reference to both the Arabic text and the English edition of *Tārīkh*. First I reference the part and page of the Arabic text by using the abbreviation TT (*Tārīkh al-Ṭabarī*), and then I reference the part and page of the English text using the abbreviation TTe (*Tārīkh al-Ṭabarī* English). The English translation has two page numbers: I firstly mention the page of the books containing the translation and secondly the page number of the Leiden manuscript on which the English translation is based. For example: TT:1:398, TTe:4:130/748. See section 2.2 for a more detailed explanation of the referral method. Full reference to the texts and the translators can be found in the bibliography.

The restriction of this research to the period from Ādam to Muḥammad is chosen because the material of the period before Muḥammad is qualitatively different from the period around and after Muḥammad. The period before Muḥammad contains a lot of material about events that modern historians doubt actually took place, while events that took place around and after the life of the Prophet Muḥammad are more often considered historically reliable.¹² Also in *Tārīkh* itself, there is a distinction between the two parts. Namely, the method that Ṭabarī applies in the first part differs from the method in the second part. In the introduction of *Tārīkh*, Ṭabarī himself states that the main source for gaining history knowledge are traditions that come from persons who have seen the events themselves.¹³ This the case for the time around and after the Prophet Muḥammad, but often not for the period before that. This is clearly reflected in the first part where his main sources are narrators describing events they claim to know to have taken place, without being a witness. Also, a lot of information about this time has come from other traditions rather than witness reports, like the Jewish, Christian, Persian and Arab traditions. Thus, although Ṭabarī sets out to maintain his strictly empirical method as consistently as possible throughout his work, the first part of *Tārīkh* is characterized primarily by the use of sources that have not been eyewitnesses to the events that they describe.

In addition, there is a clear distinction concerning the content of the two sections. In the period before Muḥammad, prophets played an important role in history. The focus of the history in this section is on the messages that the prophets bring to kings or folks and the prophets' adventures they encounter. In the section around and after Muḥammad, the prophecies stop and the focus of the narrative shifts to the developments in the (proto-)Islamic empire from an insider perspective. This shift is also clearly seen in the text itself. Right before Ṭabarī begins the section about the life of Muḥammad [ca. 570 CE], he first completes the history of the Persian royal family up to and including Yazdagird III [632-651 CE], the last king of the Sassanid dynasty. Thus Ṭabarī first finishes the history of the other peoples before moving on a perspective centered around Muhammad and the Muslim community. All in all, the first part of *Tārīkh* is thus qualitatively, methodologically, and substantively different from the section of and after Prophet Muḥammad.

¹² Terence Lovat and Amir Moghadam, *The History of Islam: Revelation, Reconstruction or Both?* (Cham: Springer, 2018), 28-29 and 48.

¹³ TT:1:11, TTe:1:170/6-7.

The choice then to take the first part, the part from Ādam to Muḥammad, as the subject for this research, stems from two considerations: first, this part of *Tārīkh* is more limited in size than the part around and after Muḥammad. The first part covers about fifteen percent of the entire work while the period around and after Muḥammad covers the rest of the work. Due to the limited time I have for this research this makes it possible to engage in a meaningful analysis of the material. Secondly, this section is chosen because the first part of *Tārīkh* has rarely been the subject of prior research. The numerous studies that have been done on Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh* focus mainly on the period around and after Prophet Muḥammad. It sometimes even seems the first part is skipped by default in these studies. There are several possible explanations for this. The uncertainty about the historical character of the events described could be a reason for other researchers not to investigate the material further. Also, the somewhat chaotic nature of the first part may be a reason that many researchers do not actively engage with this part of *Tārīkh*. The last reason may be the case since Ṭabarī constantly introduces new names and events in this part and he also frequently gives conflicting information about the course and chronology of the events in this period. By choosing the first part of *Tārīkh* as the subject of this research, I hope to attract more academic attention to this part. The new findings from the analysis as well as the family tree, which will be presented shortly, will hopefully make this part of *Tārīkh* more accessible and clear. The family tree can also function as a framework for other researchers to understand or analyze this part more easily.

In the first part of *Tārīkh*, there are about two thousand individuals mentioned by name spread over 586 pages¹⁴. Including all these individuals in the family tree would unfortunately require too much time. Therefore, the persons mentioned in Persian history will not be included in this study. The choice not to include Persian history stems from the fact that, in order to assess and understand this history, a lot of background information is required that differs from the background information necessary for understanding Arab and Israelite history. That is, an adequate study of Persian material would require a thorough study of the history and cosmology of Zoroastrianism and knowledge of the Persian royal house, Persian myths, and political history. This is knowledge I do not yet have and it would take too much time to acquire for the limited scope of this thesis.

¹⁴ Which corresponds to parts one through six page 43 (1123 pages) of the thirty-eight volume English translation of *Tārīkh*.

Excluding the persons mentioned in Persian history, more than twelve hundred individuals remain. These will all be included in the family tree. Such a family tree has not been created before. Distinctive about this family tree is that all persons mentioned in the first part of *Tārīkh* are included in one overview, not just the figures that are considered important. In addition, creating a family tree based on one work is also unique. Often a family tree is created based on multiple works so that the vision of an individual author disappears into the background. In this study, only the text of *Tārīkh* will be used. In this way, it will be possible to gain insight into the genealogy from Ādam to Muḥammad from Ṭabarī's perspective.¹⁵ Finally, the visualization of the family tree is also unique. By using digital drawing software,¹⁶ it is possible to display the family tree on one page, making the structure clear at a glance. This was previously not possible on paper.

The structure of the thesis is as follows: In chapter 1 I will first delve deeper into previous research on Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh*. For this, the studies of Newby and Mårtensson will be discussed. At the end of this chapter, the Islamic theological view of the material in the first part of *Tārīkh* is also discussed. This will show that the material is considered problematic by several Muslim scholars writing from an Islamic theological perspective. In chapter 2, the family tree will be introduced and the decisions I made when compiling the family tree will be explained and justified. The text used for the creation of the genealogy and the reference system which I used will also be discussed here. In chapters 3 and 4, the genealogical information in *Tārīkh* is analyzed. In chapter 3 'time' is discussed and in chapter 4 'space'. In these chapters, the choice of 'time' and 'space' is first explained, after which we take a look at how these elements are reflected in *Tārīkh* and how these elements are reflected in the genealogical information. The chapters each conclude with a conclusion in which the findings of the analysis are forged into a comprehensive theory. The last chapter, chapter 5, is the conclusion. Here I will answer the research question mentioned above and I will reflect on this research and its potential for the future.

¹⁵ In hindsight this statement in my thesis should be a bit more nuanced. After all, Ṭabarī relied heavily on the information supplied to him by scholars before his time. He uses these materials and puts them in an order that seems most suitable to him. Calling this end product Ṭabarī's 'own' perspective is therefore a bit out of place. In the current version I have tried to bring this nuance more to the foreground. Anyway, in paragraph 5.1 of my thesis I even discuss this issue but it should have been addressed sooner.

¹⁶ See paragraph 2.1.

1 Ṭabarī's History

In this chapter, I will discuss prior research on Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh*. The purpose of this chapter is to present a scientific framework that contributes to the understanding and contextualization of *Tārīkh*. First, the book *The Making Of The Last Prophet* by Gordon Darnell Newby on Islamic prophets is discussed. This book provides more insight into the function of prophet stories in historiography. Next, the book on Ṭabarī's law school by Ulrika Mårtensson's is discussed. Her book will provide insight into Ṭabarī's motivation to write a history. Finally, there will be a brief discussion of the appreciation of Israelite and Persian historical material from an Islamic theological perspective.¹⁷ This will show that some Muslim Islamic theological scholars question the religious authority of the material in the first part of *Tārīkh*. The family tree that will be presented in the next chapter can therefore by no means be seen as representative of an Islamic theological view on genealogy or history.

1.1 *The Making Of The Last Prophet*

Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh* is widely used in research. Sometimes it is used as a historical source and other times the work itself is the subject of research.¹⁸ In these studies, particular attention is paid to the part of *Tārīkh* about the life of Muḥammad and onwards. Research within the research field of Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh* that deals more with the literary side of the material in *Tārīkh*, such as the work of Boaz Shoshan and Johan

¹⁷ Islamic theological scholars here refer to scholars who conduct research from an Islamic theological perspective. That is, these scholars conduct their research within the framework of Islamic tradition and is thereby not confined to just theology but other sciences as well. For example, from *Tārīkh* and Ṭabarī's other works we can sense a Islamic theological perspective because the research is conducted largely within the limits of the Islamic tradition as in the works the Qur'an and the sayings of the prophet Muḥammad (*Hadīth*) are given an exalted status as a source of knowledge.

¹⁸ Two examples of prominent works in the field of early Islamic history that use *Tārīkh* as a source: Marshall G. S Hodgson, *The Venture of Islam: Conscience and History in a World Civilization* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1974), vol. 1. (The work does not contain a complete bibliography so it does not reference *Tārīkh* directly. However, on pages 356-357, footnote 14, he describes that *Tārīkh* is a crucial source of knowledge about early Islamic history which is in turn the subject of Hodgson's book); Hugh Kennedy, *The Early Abbasid Caliphate: A Political History* (Oxford: Routledge, 2016). This version is a reissue, the original work was published in 1981. See bibliography at the end of almost every chapter in this work for references to *Tārīkh*.

Two examples of works where *Tārīkh* is the subject of research: Lovat and Moghadam, *The History of Islam*; Erling Ladewig Petersen, *ʿAlī and Muʿāwiya in Early Arabic Tradition*, translated by P. Lamp Christensen (Copenhagen: Munksgaard, 1964).

Weststeijn¹⁹, is also almost exclusively concerned with the period after Muḥammad. The usefulness of the findings of these studies for establishing a scientific framework for understanding the first part of *Tārīkh* is limited. As already mentioned in the introduction²⁰, the first part of *Tārīkh* differs much from the rest of the work: the sources mentioned are different, the historicity of the events described differs, and the content of the parts differs. It is therefore difficult to estimate to what extent the findings from these studies can also be applied to the period before Muḥammad.

One of the few researchers who does pay attention to the material from the first part of *Tārīkh* is Gordon Darnell Newby. In his book, *The Making Of The Last Prophet*, Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh* is treated indirectly. The purpose of the book is to reconstruct the 'lost' first part of the biography *Sīrat rasūl Allāh* ('The Life of the Messenger of God') by the historian Ibn Ishāq [d.150/767].²¹ The biography is one of the earliest sources on the life of the Prophet Muḥammad and is therefore highly regarded by scholars and historians. However, the first part of this work has been 'lost' because today only the adaptation of Ibn Ishāq's work, made by Ibn Hishām [d. 218/833], remains. This version omits a lot of material from the first part of the *Sīra*. According to Newby, Ibn Hishām had shortened the first part of the *Sīra* because the Israelite prophet stories mentioned therein had fallen into disuse as a legitimate source of knowledge among Islamic scholars at the end of the first/beginning of the second century (i.e. 9th century).²² In his book, Newby is able to partially reconstruct the first part of Ibn Ishāq's work because Ṭabarī quotes the original work of Ibn Ishāq extensively in his *Tārīkh*.²³ So to consider the first part as 'lost' is not entirely justified. Moreover, since Ṭabarī quotes so much from the work of Ibn Ishāq, it seems that Ṭabarī was in possession of (large parts of) the original work of Ibn Ishāq which indicates that at the time of the composition of *Tārīkh*, which was completed in the early

¹⁹ Boaz Shoshan, *Poetics of Islamic Historiography: Deconstructing Ṭabarī's History* (Leiden: Brill, 2004); Johan Weststeijn, 'Dreams of Abbasid Caliphs: Suspense and Tragedy in al-Ṭabarī's History of Prophets and Kings,' *Oriens* 38, no. 1–2 (January 2010): 17–34.

²⁰ See p. 7-8.

²¹ Gordon Darnell Newby, *The Making of the Last Prophet: A Reconstruction of the Earliest Biography of Muhammad* (Columbia: University of South Carolina Press, 1989), 1.

²² Newby, *Last Prophet*, 4.

²³ Newby, *Last Prophet*, 15-16. Newby uses a number of other sources to reconstruct the first part of the *Sīra*. However, as he points out, *Tārīkh* was the main source of his reconstruction. According to Newby, Ṭabarī's work is the best source because he received Ibn Ishāq's work through his closest disciple, Salamah. However, it should be noted that it is possible that Ṭabarī, or one of his sources, edited the work of Ibn Ishāq. It is therefore questionable to what extent the reconstruction accurately represents Ibn Ishāq's original work.

4th/10th century, the prophet stories had not yet disappeared. Thus, Newby's conclusion about the disuse of prophet stories does not seem to accord entirely with the evidence that *Tārīkh* forms.

Nevertheless, Newby's work offers an interesting approach to studying prophet narratives. His theory is that the prophet stories in the first part of the *Sīra* serve to confirm the prophethood of the prophet Muḥammad, which is discussed later in the *Sīra*.²⁴ Newby thus discusses in his book each of the prophetic stories originating from Ibn Ishāq and tries to find elements in these stories which have a remarkable similarity with Ibn Ishāq's description of the events in the life of the prophet Muḥammad. In most cases, he succeeds in linking these stories to that of the prophet Muhammad. Sometimes these similarities are very apparent, the coming of Muḥammad as a prophet is for instance predicted by earlier prophets, and other times less so, there are only special similarities between the prophet stories and the description of the life of Muḥammad.²⁵

Since Ṭabarī makes extensive use of Ibn Ishāq's work, including the lineages mentioned therein, it is relevant to see if Newby's approach also applies to the genealogical structure in Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh*. In other words, do earlier prophets in the genealogy have a function in confirming the prophethood of Muḥammad from a genealogical perspective? And if so, how does it execute this function?

1.2 *Madhhab Jarī*

A much-discussed topic in the research field of Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh* is his motivation for writing a historical work. After all, it is law rather than history that seems to have been his main profession. Researchers such as Lovat and Moghadam conclude that Ṭabarī wrote the work to create an orthodoxy that would exclude other "incorrect"

²⁴ Newby, *Last Prophet*, 2.

Boaz Shoshan tries a similar approach in a small part of his work. He notes that the history on the time before Muḥammad contains parallels which can be used to understand Ṭabarī's view on the history after Muḥammad. For example, he sees a connection between the discussion of the episode of Mūsā's conflict with the Pharaoh and the rebellion of the Qarmatians, a group that rebels against the Abbasid authority in late third / beginning ninth century. Shoshan argues that the similarities in the discussion of these two "rebels" are intended to place the Qaramites on Pharaoh's wrong path. Boaz Shoshan, *Poetics*, 92-97.

²⁵ An example of a direct way in which the earlier prophets are connected to Muhammad is the case of Isaiah who predicting the coming of a final Messiah. An example of an indirect link can be seen in the story of Shu'ayb where Shu'ayb is excluded from and made fun of by his people, just as happened with Muḥammad in Mecca when he started his prophethood. Newby, *Last Prophet*, 99,174.

interpretations of history.²⁶ Others see the work simply as a collection of stories written down so that they would be preserved, as Jacob Lassner would have suggested according to Weststeijn's article.²⁷ But rarely is it discussed why Ṭabarī would have done so: Why would Ṭabarī want to create an orthodoxy? Why would Ṭabarī want to preserve these historical traditions? And how does this fit in with what we know about Ṭabarī?

The recently published book *Al-Ṭabarī's Madhhab Jarīrī* by Ulrika Mårtensson attempts to answer these questions. The reasoning in the book can be understood as follows: the word *madhhab*, which was previously translated in this thesis as law school²⁸, also simply means 'method'. *Madhhab Jarīrī*, Ṭabarī's law school, can therefore also simply be read as 'the *Jarīrī* method'. In other words, "the *Jarīrī* law school" can be understood as referring to the scientific institute that Ṭabarī tried to establish where the "*Jarīrī* method" was applied. This method then relates not only to legal works but also to other scientific disciplines and can best be understood as a set of principles for acquiring knowledge and truth. What Mårtensson tries to do in her book is to bring to light the method (*madhhab*), or paradigm, that Ṭabarī applies in his works in order to discover what the *madhhab jarīrī* is about.²⁹ She tries to achieve this by discussing all of Ṭabarī's works that are still available one by one and looking at which methodological principles play an important role in these works.³⁰ Below I will discuss only one of the methodological principles, the principle that most relates to *Tārīkh*.

The central methodological principle that Mårtensson discerns in *Tārīkh* is the "covenant theory". This refers to a covenant between God and mankind.³¹ This covenant records that God and mankind have certain rights to uphold and duties to perform: God cares (materially) for mankind and mankind should be grateful to Him and perform the religious tasks they are required to perform.³² These tasks include, for example, religious rituals, such as pilgrimage (*ḥajj*), almsgiving (*zakāt*), and fasting (*ṣawm*), but also the observance of important moral values such as justice.³³ Justice

²⁶ Promiset en Moghadam, *The History of Islam*, 51.

²⁷ Johan Weststeijn, 'Dreams of Abbasid Caliphs', 19-20.

²⁸ See p. 5.

²⁹ Ulrika Mårtensson, *Al-Ṭabarī's madhhab jarīrī* (Piscataway: Gorgias Press, November 2022), XIV.

³⁰ See Chapter 4: Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 161-258.

³¹ See Chapter 1: Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 1-34.

³² Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 48-49.

³³ Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 221, 307.

means that people had to be righteous to each other, God, and his creation.³⁴ Ultimately, *Tārīkh* plays an important role in explaining this covenant. In *Tārīkh*, the actions of kings are discussed and we can tell from the consequences of these acts whether they were righteous acts or not. If the actions are unjust, God will weaken His care and the country will suffer, if the actions are just, prosperity will follow. To illustrate this role of *Tārīkh*, Mårtensson gives as an example the rights of agricultural workers. When the rights of farm workers are not respected by a king, unrest will unravel, the king will lose his grip on the country, and chaos/sin will ensue. It's thus the king's responsibility to not let this happen.³⁵ The kings are not alone in *Tārīkh*. God sends messengers to them with wisdom to keep them on the right path. This also relates well to the title of the work: The History of Messengers and Kings.³⁶ In short, *Tārīkh* can thus be read as a collection of concrete historical events that illustrate the content of the covenant.³⁷

Mårtensson's book provides a valuable perspective into the relevance that *Tārīkh* may have had for the administrative present of Ṭabarī's time. In Chapter 4, a similar approach will be taken in the analysis of space. There we will try to connect genealogical data with the covenant theory in order to explore the administrative relevance of this information.

1.3 Isrā'īliyyāt

In the foregoing, we have seen that (some) stories mentioned in *Tārīkh* may serve as examples for kings and leaders to rule justly. Still, the material from the first part of *Tārīkh* was rarely, if ever, used in Islamic law (*fiqh*). This is because much of the material in this part was classified as: '*Isrā'īliyyāt*'. Shari L. Lowin describes *Isrā'īliyyāt* as follows:

'Isrā'īliyyāt (sing., isrā'īliyya) are narrative supplements, both historical and homiletic, that provide background material for biblical characters appearing in the Qur'ān, as well for extra-Qur'ānic biblical or legendary figures, some of whom are seen as connected to events and people from the ancient Israelite

³⁴ Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 49.

³⁵ Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 119-128.

³⁶ Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 1-5.

³⁷ See chapters 1 and 3: Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jwuldīrī* 1-34, 97-160.

In support of the view that the work was intended for kings and leaders, it can be argued that literacy in Ṭabarī's time was very low and copying books very expensive. As a result, the work was only accessible to the (governing) elite of the empire who were able to study.

period. These are not, however, always Jewish or Christian in origin and can sometimes be found in Zoroastrian or other Near Eastern cultures.³⁸

Thus, the category "*Isrā'īliyyāt*" refers to the material on prophets, heroes, and important individuals in the past that comes from non-Quranic sources. The context and additional information that this material provides about Israelite, and sometimes Persian, (prophet) history, was part of the Islamic tradition from early on. Lowin describes that these non-Quranic stories played an important role in understanding Islam for many Muslims from the time of the Prophet Muḥammad onward. According to Lowin they often served to place the prophethood of the prophet Muḥammad in prophetic history, as in line with Newby's approach³⁹, but it was also sporadically used to understand matters about which Muḥammad had not ruled.⁴⁰ This latter approach was justified by the Quranic verse 10:94: "If you are in doubt about what We have sent down to you, then ask those who have been reading the book before you."⁴¹

Many important companions of the Prophet Muḥammad such as the well-known companion Abdallah Ibn 'Abbās [d. 68/687] specialized in non-Quranic material. In the decades that followed after the passing of Muhammad, as many Jews and Christians converted to Islam, more and more specialized knowledge about Jewish and Christian sources and history came into the Muslim community. Wahb ibn Munabbih [d. 144/738], possibly the most famous convert who functioned as *Isrā'īliyyāt* transmitter, is an example of this. However, according to Lowin, this non-Quranic material was increasingly viewed with suspicion by scholars from the third/ninth centuries onwards. This is around the period when Islamic law became fully institutionalized. Scholars believed that the non-Quranic material might have been corrupted, as one can only be sure that the word of God in the Quran is unfillable. These doubts about the soundness of the material made it unusable as a source for Islamic laws and precepts. The *Isrā'īliyyāt* material was thus almost completely excluded from Islamic law.⁴²

³⁸ Shari L. Lowin, 'Isrā'īliyyāt,' in *Encyclopaedia of Islam THREE*, edited by Kate Fleet, Gudrun Krämer, Denis Matringe, John Nawas, and Devin J. Stewart, Published 2019, accessed online February 6, 2023. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_ei3_COM_32621.

³⁹ See paragraph 1.1.

⁴⁰ Shari L. Lowin, 'Isrā'īliyyāt.'

⁴¹ 'Those who have been reading the book before you' mainly refers to Jews and Christians who previously received 'the book' (The Torah and Bible). Quran translation is from Lowin's article.

⁴² Shari L. Lowin, 'Isrā'īliyyāt.'

Yet, despite the doubts about its reliability, we do see a lot of Isrāʿīlyyāt material returning in other sciences such as Quranic exegesis (*tafsīr*) and history (*tārīkh*).⁴³ This is clearly reflected in the first part of Ṭabarī's *Tārīkh* in which the Isrāʿīlyyāt material is frequently cited and the aforementioned Ibn ʿAbbās and Ibn Munabbih are among the most cited sources. In addition, the material also has a huge popularity among Muslims outside of Islamic theological sciences. This can be seen, for example, in the stories known to us as Arabian Nights or 1001 Nights, in which many Persian elements return such as Mount *Qāf* and the bird *Simorgh*. But also the very popular *Shahmaneh* of Abū-I-Qāsim Firdawsī [d. 410/1020] which describes Persian (heroic) history up to the advent of Islam, the many references in prose and poems to the Persian and Israelite prophets and the popularity of Jewish and Christian mystical prophet stories in Islamic mysticism⁴⁴ are examples that the Isrāʿīlyyāt-material was used by Muslims to entertain and inspire other Muslims. Thus, there can be no doubt that the Isrāʿīlyyāt-material did play an important role throughout history in the meaning-making of Islam for many Muslims.

In recent times, according to Lowin, the name "Isrāʿīlyyāt" has taken on an even more negative connotation among a sizeable proportion of Islamic scholars. This trend is attributed to the rise of the influential twentieth-century Islamic reform movements. According to these reformers, the Isrāʿīlyyāt material is separate from "pure Islam" and only the Qur'an and prophetic traditions serve as a source for any legitimate Islamic knowledge and wisdom.⁴⁵ Although Ṭabarī had and has a lot of prestige as a scholar, the family tree that will be presented in the current research will therefore be of limited significance to some Islamic theological scholars and Muslims because it is largely based on Isrāʿīlyyāt material. The family tree can thus not be seen as a representative of an Islamic theological view on history or genealogy. The family tree will only try to do justice to and contribute to the understanding of those Muslims and Islamic theological scholars, including Ṭabarī, who do consider this material to be meaningful and valuable.

⁴³ Shari L. Lowin, 'Isrāʿīlyyāt.'

⁴⁴ For example, the strong parables in the material of the Biblical Elijah and Al-Khiḍr, both of whom acquire immortality and enormous wisdom. For the Islamic representation of Elijah, see for example the poem *Eskandar-Nāmeḥ* (The Book of Alexander the Great) by Nezami [d. 605-6/1209]. See: Patrick Franke, 'Khiḍr,' in *Encyclopaedia of Islam THREE*, edited by Kate Fleet, Gudrun Krämer, Denis Matringe, John Nawas, and Devin J. Stewart, published 2022, accessed online February 6, 2023. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_ei3_COM_35534.

⁴⁵ Shar L. Lowin, 'Isrāʿīlyyāt.'

2 The Family Tree: Explanation & Accountability

To investigate the function of the genealogical information, I will present the information in the form of a family tree. The family tree itself and instructions for viewing it can be found in Appendix A. In this chapter, I'll explain and justify the choices I made during its creation. First of all, I'll briefly describe how the family tree came about. Then I'll explain the following four topics: (1) the version of *Tārīkh* used to create the family tree along with the corresponding registration method, (2) the selection criteria used when including individuals into the family tree, (3) the meaning and choice of the colors in the family tree and (4) how I dealt with multiple (alternative) genealogies. At the end of the chapter, there is a brief reflection on what can be learned from the visualization concerning the function of the genealogical information in *Tārīkh*.

Figure 1. Family tree overview (See Appendix A)

2.1 Family tree

While reading the first part of *Tārīkh*, I noticed that, at times, it can be difficult to follow. The main reason for this is the form of the text itself. Ṭabarī uses traditions that he has received directly or indirectly from other historians/scholars. Ṭabarī usually uses multiple traditions about the a single event to describe some part of the history. These traditions can be very different in their description of the events or they can even be contradictory. It is often unclear which of these traditions enjoys Ṭabarī's preference and so the reader is left with a patchy description of history. This, as well as the sheer scale of the work, makes it often difficult to understand exactly how Ṭabarī envisions history in his *Tārīkh*. To gain a better understanding of the first part of *Tārīkh* I turned my attention to the enormous amount of names and lineages mentioned throughout *Tārīkh*. In September 2021, the idea arose to organize this genealogical information and process it into a family tree. The first question was whether the genealogical information provided by Ṭabarī would have any consistency at all, since Ṭabarī uses a wide variety of sources. But when this turned out to be the case, the idea to create a full overview of the genealogical data arose.

The family tree started on paper, but because of the frequent changes that had to be made and the enormous size of the family tree, a switch was made to a digital version. Finding a suitable genealogy program was not easy. The program had to have a lot of flexibility to be able to process all the information. Some individuals for instance have multiple partners and others have multiple lineages because Ṭabarī's sources each mention a different lineage. In order to display the genealogical information carefully and include all the nuances the information contained, it had to be possible to process this information into the family tree. Despite the large amount of genealogy programs, none fulfilled the requirements. A simple drawing program, LibreOffice Draw, was therefore used to create the digital family tree.⁴⁶ With this program, it is possible to place (text) boxes, lines, and signs on a large canvas. This provided a lot of freedom in the design of the family tree. The enormous freedom also made it possible to process additional information in the family tree that gives the relationships in the family tree more depth, such as the function of a person or the length of the reign of kings. The disadvantage of using a drawing program is that all

⁴⁶ The inspiration for using this drawing program to create the family tree came from the Youtube channel 'Useful Charts'. See: <https://www.youtube.com/@UsefulCharts>.

boxes, lines, and characters have to be placed, adjusted, and aligned separately. In addition, the program does not have a standard model for creating a family tree, so all elements in the family tree had to be designed themselves. A simple change in the design or an adjustment to the family tree meant that sometimes hundreds of elements had to be changed manually. Making simple adjustments could therefore take anywhere from half an hour to a whole day or, in some cases, even several days.

The next task was to track down all the names in the studied part of *Tārīkh*. Unfortunately, there is no register available with all names, and finding the names in the Arabic version is difficult since it does not use capital letters. To be as efficient as possible, I used the following method: I used the English translation of *Tārīkh* to find the names. Then I determined whether it was the name of a person or something else, such as an animal, place, fortress, river, spirit, etc., or whether this person had already appeared earlier in the history under a different name.⁴⁷ Next, I looked for this name in the Arabic text. Because there is no consistency in the page numbering or layout between the Arabic and English text I used, it was often only clear where the name would be approximately. This meant I often had to read through large parts of the Arabic text to find the names. Then it was important to check whether the Arabic name was similar in spelling to the other Arabic names in the family tree. Sometimes the English translation or transcription of a name could obscure the fact that a person was mentioned before. Using the Arabic text proved very valuable since there appeared to be minor inconsistencies between the English translation and the Arabic text. As a final step, I added the person to the genealogy and entered the page number, along with several other data, into a register so that the genealogy would be verifiable for others.⁴⁸

⁴⁷ It often happens that names are written differently in different places in the text. For example, Qāyn whose name also written as 'Qābīl', 'Qayn' and 'Qābīn'. See TT:1:90, TTe: 1:307/137.

⁴⁸ See below at '2.2 Register and Text' for an explanation of the register.

The process of creating the family tree took over a year and a half to complete because of the search for names and the time-consuming adjustments. The family tree was final, except for a small number of adjustments, in January 2023. During those one and a half years many changes have been made and, as mentioned earlier, this meant that all lines and boxes had to be realigned manually every time. Despite many checks and my spacious time investment, there are different places in the family tree where lines and boxes that do not exactly align fully; The family tree is not so to say 'pixel-perfect'. However, these minor inconsistencies do not affect clarity. In the picture below you can find an explanation of the basic elements of the family tree. Here you can see what information is included in the family tree. In the paragraphs below, I will explain and justify the choices I made in the making of the genealogy further.

Figure 2. Explanation of basic elements of family tree.

2.2 Text & Register

The text used to compile the family tree is taken from *Tārīkh al-Ṭabarī: Tārīkh al-ummam wa-l-mulūk*, compiled by Muḥammad Abū I-Faḍl Ibrāhīm, published by *Dar Iḥyā' al-Turāth al-'Arabī*. In this thesis and in the immediately introduced register, this text is referred to by the abbreviation TT (*Tārīkh al-Ṭabarī*), followed by the part and page where the information can be found. To increase verifiability and make the family tree accessible to non-Arabic reading researchers, a second reference to the English translation has also been added. The abbreviation for the translation is TTe (*Tārīkh al-Ṭabarī* English) and is also followed by the volume and the page number. The English translation has two page numbers: the numbering of the translation itself and the numbering of the Leiden manuscript on which the translation is based. Both page numbers will be mentioned in the reference. First, the page number of the translation is mentioned, and then the page of the Leiden Manuscript. The page numbering of the Leiden Manuscript is mentioned so that it is easier for other researchers to find the names when working with this manuscript. In Figure 3 you can find an example of a reference. The part used for this research of the ten-volume Arabic version is volume one to volume two page 176. This matches with volumes one to volume six page 43 of the thirty-eight volume English translation. In this thesis, the same method of referral as in the register has been used. In the bibliography of this thesis, the full references to the texts used can be found.

To create the genealogy I used the Arabic version as my main source. The names in the family tree are therefore displayed in Arabic. To make the family tree accessible to non-Arabic readers, a transcription has also been added to each name. For many names, it is not known exactly how to pronounce them. Thus, the transcription is an approximation of the pronunciation of the name. Sometimes the transcription from the English translation is used but they do not vocalize all the names or use

the English version of a name. Moreover, the transcription in the English version sometimes does not correspond to the Arabic version in which some names are (partly) vocalized. As a solution to the problem, when in doubt about the pronunciation of a name, I decided to place an *a* (a *fatha*) between the consonants so that the names could be pronounced. The family tree cannot therefore be used to find out the correct pronunciation of a name, the transliteration is purely functional. Because the Arabic text is taken as the basis for the family tree, Arabic text appears in several places in the visualization. For example, at the bottom of some name boxes, there is 'additional information'. Due to a lack of space, it was not possible to present this information in English. The information that is untranslated only concerns less essential information, such as the function of a person and the reign period of kings. In general I have tried to use visual, rather than textual, elements as much as possible to make the family tree understandable to all.

To make the family tree verifiable, each person in the family tree is provided with a reference number. With that number, the person can be looked up in the corresponding register (see Appendix A). In this, I have registered six data of each individual: (1) the reference number, (2) the Arabic name, (3) the sex, (4) nicknames and names that are written differently but refer to the same person⁴⁹, (5) a reference to the page where the genealogy of the person is mentioned, and (6) particularities in establishing the pedigree of a person. In Figure 4 the beginning of the register is displayed. Column 6 is not visible in the figure because it is too big. Nearly 1300 individuals can be found in the register. When, from this point on, I refer to a person in the family tree, then there I'll add the reference number to the name. This makes the person easy to find in the family tree and register.

⁴⁹ It is, for instance, common in Arabic for people to have nicknames. It is also possible that a non-Arabic name has been transcribed into Arabic in different ways by Ṭabarī's sources, so there are different spellings of the same name throughout *Tārīkh*. For use nicknames in Arabic, see: Bearman, P., Bianquis, Th., et al, 'Ism,' in *Encyclopaedia of Islam Second Edition*, edited by P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs, et al., published 1978, accessed online April 19, 2023. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_SIM_3641.

NUMBER	NAME	MALE / FEMALE	ALTERNATIVE NAME	SOURCE (explanation at the end)
1	آدم	m		TT:1:61, TTe: 1:257/86
2	حواء	f		TT:1:69, TTe: 1:273/102
3	أمة المغيث	f		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:316/146
4	عبد المغيث	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:316/146
5	عبد الحارث	m		TT:1:96, TTe: 1:320/149
6	بارق	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
7	سندل	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
8	يحدود	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
9	هدز	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
10	ضرابيس	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
11	حيان	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
12	شبوية	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
13	بنان	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
14	توية	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
15	أثائي	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
16	بالغ	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
17	أباد	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
18	شيث	m	شاث, شت, هبة الله	TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
19	حزورة	f	عزورا	TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
20	ليوذا	f		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:317/146
21	هابيل	m		TT:1:90, TTe: 1:307/137
22	قليما	f		TT:1:93, TTe: 1:314/144
23	قايين	m	قابيل, قين, قابين	TT:1:90, TTe: 1:307/137
24	أشوت	f		TT:1:95, TTe: 1:317/146
25	أنوش	m	يانش	TT:1:106, TTe:1:335/164
26	نعمة	f		TT:1:106, TTe:1:335/164
27	براكليل	m		TT:1:106, TTe:1:336/165
28	خنوخ	m	أخنوخ	TT:1:108, TTe: 1:337/167

Figure 4. Start of registry. Column six is next to SOURCE but is too wide to include in this view.

2.3 Selection of People

In order to enable the visualization of genealogy, it is necessary to establish a number of guidelines for who to include. This is important because it prevents the family tree from becoming messy with people who add little to our understanding of the genealogy. In total, there are four guidelines which I have drawn up. First, in the period between Ādam and Muḥammad, in addition to names of persons, the names of several other beings such as horses, jinns, angels, and idols appear in *Tārīkh*. I decided not to include these other creatures in the family tree because they have no genealogical connection with humans. The family tree thus consists only of people. Secondly, only persons who are mentioned by name in the text are included in the family tree. Any nicknames are also sufficient because naming a person by their nickname is in some cases more common than their "proper" name.⁵⁰ All persons without a name, such as "an uncle on his father's side", "a cousin of ..." or "three men of

⁵⁰ See footnote 47. An example of a person who is only mentioned by a nickname is Muhaddid (297). This name refers to her role in the story as a warner and is not her own name. See: TT:1:145, TTe:2:35/239.

Quraysh", are not included. These people are difficult to include in the family tree because it is not always clear what the family relationship looks like (i.e. which uncle? Is this a full uncle? Is it really an uncle or is this person like an uncle to a certain person?). Moreover, the inclusion of these individuals adds little to the understanding of the family tree. That person X "has an uncle" says little about person X without further explanation. Adding these people would therefore make the family tree clogged with unnamed figures.

Thirdly, individuals who have a name but no lineage or a lineage that doesn't connect to the main genealogy will be placed near other people with whom they appear together in the history. For example, Zarah (484) is mentioned as the king of India and since he has no lineage he is placed near the Israelite Asā (483) because they appear together in a story. In this way, individuals who lived at about the same time are grouped together and it becomes easy to see to which part of history they belong to. Finally, in a fair number of cases, only the distant ancestor of a person is known and not a direct lineage. When this is the case, this person is placed near the ancestor and connected to this ancestor by a dotted line with the accompanying text 'Of the tribe/sons of ...' (*min banū ...*). This means it is unclear how many generations there are between them and their ancestor, so it may be that this person lived much later than the ancestor with whom he/she is connected. An example of this is Zamrī (388) who is only mentioned as a descendent of Sham'ūn (365) and so we do not know exactly how the two are connected.

There are two exceptions to these rules. An exception has been made for 'Āj (446). According to the text, he is from among the giants (*al-jabbārīn*)⁵¹ But in this research, giants are considered to be human (or perhaps more appropriately human-like?). This is motivated by the fact that there are also humans who are very big (just like giants, such as Ādam (1)⁵²), but which are not called giants. Also, there are exceptions to the rule that a person should be mentioned by name. This applies to the ancestors of Luqmān (258), the wife of 'Amr (352i), two wives of Sulaymān (466), and the uncle of Ishther (544) (see Figure 5). They have received a place in the family tree because they form a family link between individuals who do have a name.

⁵¹ TT:1:276, TTe:3:81/498.

⁵² According to a tradition of Qatāda cited by Ṭabarī Ādam shrunk to 60 *dhira'*, which, according to the English translation, is about 30 meters, after he had be larger previously. So Ādam can, at least to our modern understanding of the word, be considered a giant. See: TT:1:81, TTe:1:293/122.

This way the family relationships of more people mentioned by name can be included in the family tree.

2.4 Colors

To create some order in the visualization of the genealogical information, it is helpful to divide the family tree into sections. This also makes it easier to know where to search for a given name when looking at the genealogy from a distance. The sections are indicated by the background color of each name box. These background colors represent tribal affiliations. Persons with the same background color thus belong to the same folk or tribe. Determining who belongs to which tribe is somewhat arbitrary because Ṭabarī, or his sources, does not always indicate to which tribe someone belongs. I have tried however with uttermost care to make the subdivision of the genealogy into tribes as closely connected to the text as possible.

As an example, Sārah (221) begins the pedigree of the Israelites because the text places a lot of emphasis on the separation of the family tree at Ibrāhīm (220) between his two sons Ishāq (290) and Ismā‘īl (289). From a genealogical perspective, the distinguishing factor between these two sons is their mothers. Sārah (221), Ishāq’s (290) mother, and her descendants thus have their own unique background color to signify the Israelite branch of the genealogy. Later on in the Israelite branch, from the moment of the Babylonian captivity, which in about the 6th century CE, the pinkish color of the Israelites ends and changes to a darker color (see Figure 6). This is because Barkhiyyā (530) is the last person in the text who is mentioned in the Jewish-Israelite tradition. After describing the events of the Babylonian captivity the narrative in *Tārīkh* leaps forward and continues with the story of ‘Īsā (605) (in the Christian tradition Jesus). To show that there is a difference in the tradition the persons is mentioned in I have decided to give the individuals who are solely mentioned in the section about ‘Īsā (605) this darker background color.

In the legend of the family tree you can see which background color represents which folk or tribe. In several cases, it was difficult to determine to which tribe a person could best be counted. In those cases, I have put a note on their parentage in column 6 of the register. In a small number of cases, it was however completely unclear to which people a particular person belonged. In those cases, the background has been left white and in column 6 of the register, it is sometimes briefly mentioned why it could not be determined.⁵³ In short, the tribes have been added visually to

⁵³ An example of this is Daws Dhū Tha‘albān (338n), a Christian from the city of Najran. Possibly he belongs to the Arabs, but it is unclear which Arabs he belongs to since there are several groups of Arabs in the family tree as will be discussed later on in this Thesis. So his background is left white.

create more of an overview and may not be completely in line with how Ṭabarī would order the genealogical ties.

2.5 Alternative Genealogies

A final hurdle in creating a family tree based on *Tārīkh* is the individuals with multiple lineages. Because Ṭabarī makes use of information coming from different sources, there are several cases where an individual gets ascribed to multiple different lineages. Because the visualization of multiple lineages makes the family tree unclear, I decided to only include one lineage in the family tree in these cases while placing the other lineage under “Alternative Genealogies”. The individuals with multiple lineages

have placed next to their box a number, see Figure 2 on p. 24, which refers to a section of the alternative genealogies (Figure 7). Here I present the other lineages of the person with a reference to where these lineage(s) can be found in the text.

The consequence of choosing to include only one lineage in the family tree is that I had to make a decision on which lineage I wanted to include in the family tree and which will be placed in the alternative genealogies-section. In many cases, this was relatively simple and I could just choose

Figure 7. Alternative genealogies box.

the lineage that most closely matched the information from *Tārīkh*. However, in two cases it was more difficult to determine which lineage(s) should be placed under 'alternative'. First, alternative genealogy 10, belonging to Bukht Naṣṣr (397).⁵⁴ Ṭabarī describes him as a king in Babylon who is obedient to the Persian supreme king. The link of Bukht Naṣṣr with the Persians and the fact that a Persian lineage is also mentioned makes it plausible that he belongs to the Persian family tree and that he is not

⁵⁴ This is the same person which is known in English as king Nebuchadnezzar II who ruled Babylon in the beginning of 6th century BCE.

a descendant of Kūsh (103) like the family tree shows right now. If the Persian family tree had also been worked out, Bukht Naşsr would have ended up there. The reason why Bukht Naşsr is still mentioned as a descendant of Kūsh is because the persons between Bukht Naşsr and Kūsh possibly did exist and otherwise they could not be included.

The second debatable case is the lineage of ʿAdnān (548). His alternative genealogies are listed at 26 in the alternative genealogies box. ʿAdnān is the person with the most alternative genealogies of the entire family tree. As can be seen, the lineages are partly similar and the main difference between them is the length of the lineage (the number of generations). Ṭabarī does not indicate in *Tārīkh* which lineage he prefers, so it is difficult to determine which of these genealogies should be included in the family tree. I have chosen the current lineage based on the fact that this lineage is the most detailed and that this lineage best fits the text in terms of chronology. This means that if a shorter genealogy had been chosen, the prophet Muḥammad (924), a distant grandson of ʿAdnān, would have been in the same generation as ʿĪsā (605) which is impossible from the chronological perspective of the text.

It is, however, imperative to underscore that Ṭabarī's inclusion of multiple lineages serves a deliberate purpose. These diverse lineages may indicate an element of uncertainty in Ṭabarī's vision on a person's lineage. Most importantly, it can be inferred that Ṭabarī includes these various lineages because he accords them a degree of legitimacy. Consequently, the lineages categorized under 'alternative genealogies' should be considered with equal significance and credibility when compared to those integrated into the family tree.

2.6 Conclusion

Although the visualization of the genealogical information in the form of a family tree is only the beginning of the research into the function of this information, we can already draw an important conclusion from the visualization. The visualization of the genealogical information shows that there is a remarkable degree of consistency: many persons mentioned in *Tārīkh* have genealogical ties to other individuals in the history. Although the design choices hides some irregularities in the family tree, the consistency is very remarkable given the many different sources that Ṭabarī has

used. This indicates that this information has been handled with care. Whatever the specific function of the genealogical information was for the text and Ṭabarī, the visualization shows that a high degree of consistency was required to enable this function. In chapters 3 and 4 the family tree is further analyzed and the function of the genealogical information is investigated.

3 Findings & Analysis Time

To investigate the function of the genealogical information in *Tārīkh*, I will in this chapter analyze the family tree from the perspective of time. This perspective was chosen because it plays an important role in both historiography and genealogy. For example, every historian uses some form of time to create a chronology in the history he/she describes and genealogists make use of generations as a form of time. Studying the patterns in the handling of time in the family tree and finding out how this relates to the text of *Tārīkh* will give us more insight into the function of this information in regard to the history. Moreover, a bad or good alignment in the manner in which time is handled in the text vis-a-vis genealogy will tell us more about the interplay between genealogy in historiography. Below are presented the results of the analysis from the perspective of time.

3.1 Time In *Tārīkh*

In the introduction to *Tārīkh*, Ṭabarī pays extensive attention to the concept of time. He tries to answer questions such as: What is time? What is the function of time? And what is the length of time? This last question is of particular interest to the current research. Ṭabarī means by this that he wants to investigate how many years the world will exist from the creation of man to the destruction of man. He concludes that it will last 7000 years and that 6500 years have passed at the time of the Prophet Muḥammad.⁵⁵ He bases his conclusions on traditions of the Prophet Muḥammad. This means that the period from Ādam to Muḥammad would be 6500 years long and that the world would perish about 200 years after Ṭabarī's death.⁵⁶ This first fact is interesting because the family tree covers exactly this 6500 year-period. However, Ṭabarī doesn't do anything with this time-indication: he does not use it as an era throughout the first part of his book, nor does he explain how the 6500 years relate to the time periods in history. The latter would have been useful to get an impression of how events, and by extension people, relate to each other temporal perspective.

When we look at the text itself, we see that Ṭabarī, or his sources, indicates in a lot of places how many years there are between certain events as well as report the ages of individuals during important events or the duration of the reign of kings. An

⁵⁵ Ṭabarī's discussion of the duration of time: TT:1:13-18, TTe:1:172-186/8-18. Ṭabarī's conclusion About time: TT:1:16-17, TTe:1:183/15.

⁵⁶ Ṭabarī died in 310/922.

analysis of all these time indications in the text could possibly provide insight into how Ṭabarī's estimate of 6500 years is structured in time periods. However, such an analysis would be very time-consuming and therefore beyond the scope of this limited research. Fortunately, just before discussing the life of the Prophet Muḥammad, Ṭabarī returns to the topic of the length of time. First, he mentions how long other religious groups estimate the period between Ādam (1) and Muḥammad (924) to be after which cites five other estimates. Table 1 shows the sources cited by Ṭabarī:

Table 1: Era from Ādam to Muḥammad		
Source	Number of years between Ādam and Muḥammad	Reference
Jews	4642	TT:2:149, TTe:5:412/1068
Christians	5992	TT:2:149, TTe:5:412/1068
Zoroastrians	4152	TT:2:149, TTe:5:412/1068
Wahb Ibn Munabbih	5500 ⁵⁷	TT:2:150, TTe:5:415-6/1070-1
Ibn 'Abbās	5500	TT:2:150, TTe:5:415/1071
'Some authorities'	6133 (6186) ⁵⁸	TT:2:151, TTe:5:416/1071
Ibn 'Abbās	5750	TT:2:151, TTe:5:416/1072
People of the Book	5702	TT:2:151, TTe:5:416-17/1072

The sources in Table 1 are divided into three colors to distinguish between the types of sources. The green sources are the estimates of other religious groups as Ṭabarī reports himself. He doesn't do anything with these estimates. The blue sources are claims made by Muslim narrators about the length of time between Ādam to Muḥammad. These traditions do not contain a subdivision into time periods and so they are not very helpful in gaining more insight into the build-up of time in history. The orange sources differ from the rest in that they do contain a subdivision of time into periods. For example, Ibn 'Abbās makes a periodization based on the prophets:

⁵⁷ The tradition of Wahb ibn Munabbih indicates that 5600 years have passed since Ādam. Ṭabarī however explains that Wahb probably meant until his own time, i.e. 114 AH. To equalize the estimates, his estimate of 5600 years has been reduced by 100 years.

⁵⁸ First it is mentioned that "Some authorities" think that the world exists for 6133 years. Then there follows a division of time into periods and their duration is mentioned. When this is added up together, however, you arrive at 6186 years.

'Some authorities have related from Hishām b. Muḥammad al-Kalbī - his father - Abū Ṣāliḥ - Ibn ʿAbbās, who said that from Ādam to Nūḥ was twenty-two hundred years; from Nūḥ to Ibrāhīm, 1143 years; from Ibrāhīm to Mūsā, 575 years; from Mūsā to Dawūd, 179 years; from Dawūd to ʿĪsā, 1,053 years; and from ʿĪsā to Muḥammad, 600 years.'⁵⁹

By adding these years together, you arrive at a total of 5750 years. Ṭabarī's own estimate, that 6500 years passed from Ādam to Muḥammad, is not explained by these orange sources nor by any of the others. The orange estimates, for instance, differ from Ṭabarī's claim by 350 to 800 years. A possible explanation for why Ṭabarī does not use the 6500 years and does not account for its build-up is the nature of his claim. Ṭabarī's claim is in the introduction to *Tārīkh* where he explains his philosophical/theological view of time and the creation of the earth. Information about time and creation is impossible to obtain for an ordinary human since no one was around to witness creation, so Ṭabarī relies on a person who has special knowledge about this time, the Prophet Muhammad. In this context, he concludes that the world will exist for 7000 years and that 6500 years have passed between Ādam and Muḥammad. This thus seems to be more like a theological reasoning. When Ṭabarī continues to describe the life of the first people, we may not see these 6500 years because from this point on Ṭabarī has to adhere to the conventions of the history discipline. The history discipline most likely had different conventions about what constitutes legitimate knowledge than theology and so Ṭabarī could not just continue to use these 6500 years without citing historical sources. In other words, for Ṭabarī the time from Ādam to Muḥammad was theologically 6500 years, but historically this cannot be fully justified and so Ṭabarī does not use it when he continues to describe the history.

Although the orange traditions do not fully explain Ṭabarī's 6500 years, the time periods mentioned in these traditions will be used in the next section as a comparative source to make a global time distribution in the family tree. This makes it possible to get some insight into the temporal distribution in the family tree.

3.2 Length Time In Family Tree

For analyzing the temporal relationships between persons in the family tree, Ṭabarī's claim about the length of time, namely that 6500 years had passed at the time of

⁵⁹ TT:2:151, TTe:5:416/1072

Muḥammad's Hijra (622 CE), is taken as a starting point. The orange traditions will be used to create some sort of indication about the distribution of time. Figure 8 shows the global distribution of time in the family tree. Mūsā (427) was chosen as a rough halfway point because his year of birth can easily be determined from the orange traditions. The red part of Ādam (1), the first person in the family tree, to Mūsā (427) represents according to these traditions just under 4000 years.⁶⁰ The green line from Mūsā (427) to Muḥammad (924) thus represents the remaining 2500 years. It is noticeable that the green line is longer than the red line even though the green line represents a shorter time. Also in terms of relative distance, i.e. based on the number of generations between the persons, the green part is longer than the red part: between Ādam (1) and Mūsā (427), there are 29 generations, and between Mūsā (427) and Muḥammad (924) 49. This means that the average time between generations in the red part is $4000/29 = 138$ years and in the green part $2500/49 = 51$ years.⁶¹

⁶⁰ 'Some authorities': 2256 years from Ādam to the Flood, 1079 years from the Flood to birth Ibrāhīm, 565 years of birth Ibrāhīm to Exodus Mūsā. All together 3900 years.

Ibn 'Abbās: 2200 years of Ādam to the Flood, 1143 years from the Flood to Ibrāhīm, 575 years of Ibrāhīm to Mūsā. All together 3918 years.

Ibn 'Abbās: 2256 years of Ādam to the Flood, 1020 years from the Flood to death Ibrāhīm, 75 years of death Ibrāhīm to the entry of Egypt, 430 years from the entry of Egypt to the Exodus Mūsā. All together 3781 years.

See: TT:2:151, TTe:5:416-17/1071-72. See: TT:2:151, TTe:5:416-17/1071-72.

⁶¹ The number of generations is determined by simply counting the generations of the lineages of Ādam until Mūsā and of Mūsā until Muḥammad. This is possible because these lineages are uninterrupted.

Generations of 138 years are at first glance a bit unusual, but when we look at the text we see that the people at the beginning of the family tree are very old before they get their successor: Shīth (18) was 105 years old when he got Anūsh (25) and Yarad (45) was 162 years old when his son Akhnūkh (50) was born.⁶² After Mūsā (427), in the green part, people do not get as old at all and thus probably have children earlier. This would also explain why the average age per generation is much lower there. However, it is difficult to check whether this change in average corresponds to Ṭabarī's own image of the time because after Mūsā (427) he, nor his sources, mention how old a person is when he attains fatherhood. Unfortunately, any explanation as to why the average age drops so significantly between these parts is not provided in the text.

3.3 Unequal Lineages

In addition to studying time through time measurements such as years, it is also possible to examine time through generations. After all, the family tree is based on successive generations. When we look at the generations in the family tree the, what I termed, 'unequal' lineages stand out. This means that a lineage splits off into two lineages and that these lineages later reunite while one split has many more generations than the other. This occurs in many places in genealogy and is not limited to a particular section. The unequal lineages seem to have different causes. Below are three examples of unequal lineages with each a different possible cause.

⁶² TT:1:106 in 110, TTe:1:335/164 in 343/172.

First, we look at the lineage of Zakariyyā' (591) and 'Amrān (588). They are connected through their wives who are sisters of each other. In addition, we see in the text that they must have both lived at about the same time since they appear in the same story.⁶³ When we look at the lineages of Zakariyyā' (591) and 'Amrān (588) we see that between them and their first common ancestor Yahūshāfāz (489) are 12 and 22 generations respectively (see Figure 9). This is quite a big difference and is from a genealogical perspective not very plausible. However, this difference could be explained by the fact that the ancestors of Zakariyyā' (591) each had children relatively late in comparison to the ancestors of 'Amrān (588). Another possible explanation for this difference is that, assuming that the lineages are also historical lineages, some of the ancestors of Zakariyyā' (591) are omitted or forgotten because they were considered to be of little significance while 'Amrān's (588) were of greater significance since they were the kings of Jerusalem, and thus better recorded. Both explanations are difficult to confirm because of the ancestors of Zakariyyā' (591) virtually nothing is known.⁶⁴

Figure 9. Simplified representation of lineage of Zakariyyā' (591) and 'Amrān (588).

A different case we find at the beginning of the family tree. In Figure 10, the lineage of Ādam (1) is shown in a simplified form. The lineages of Ādam's sons, Qāyn (23) and Shīth (18), are marked blue and green. When we look at the blue lineage of Qāyn (23) we see that the fifth generation consists of four daughters. They all had a son with a man from the lineage of Shīth (18). This is remarkable since Dīna (32) marries with the third generation Shīth's (18) lineage while her sister 'Amdhara

⁶³ See: TT:1:380, TTe:4:102/711.

⁶⁴ Another example of this type of inequality is 'Adī (422j) in Raqās (422i) which are respectively 11 in 19 generations removed from their common ancestor Saba' (152).

directly connected to him. This is very plausible because the words for 'son', 'daughter', and 'descend(t of)/sons' are very similar in Arabic (ابن, ابنة, بنو).⁶⁶

3.4 Chronology

As already discussed in section 3.1, Ṭabarī does not use an era in the first part of *Tārīkh*. All Ṭabarī does is put the events in chronological order. To allow for a chronology, in a work that discusses Arab, Persian, and Israelite histories, Ṭabarī decided to take one of these histories as a chronological framework and try to roughly incorporate the other histories into its chronology. According to him, the Persian history is best suited for this because it is more reliable and complete than the other histories:

‘The history (or chronology) of the world’s bygone years is more easily explained and more clearly seen based upon the lives of the Persian kings than upon those of the kings of any other nation. For no nation but theirs among those leading their pedigree back to Ādam is known whose realm lasted and whose rule was continuous... Thus, a history based upon the lives of the Persian kings has the soundest sources and the best and clearest data.’⁶⁷

Ṭabarī’s decision to use one history as a framework for creating an overarching chronology does have a disadvantage: many events that play an important role in Israelite and Arab history are difficult to place in Persian history because these events are not mentioned in it. Nevertheless, Ṭabarī impressively manages to create a chronology that is largely in line with the current scientific consensus on the sequence of events in history.

Given Ṭabarī’s preference for Persian history, it is striking that he does not use the Persian era in any way. He is aware that there is a Persian era as he briefly mentions it in the beginning and end of the first part of *Tārīkh*.⁶⁸ However, this may have something to do with his separate appreciation of Persian chronology and era. The era of the Persians, where the number of years between Ādam and Muḥammad’s hijra is 4152 years, may be too far removed from his own view of history and the Muslim historians that went before him as shown in Table 1. The continuity of Persian history and its chronology, however, may have prompted Ṭabarī to appreciate Persian

⁶⁶ Another case where this may have happened is the case of Yaqsān (193) in Ra‘awa (192) who are one and four generations apart respectively.

⁶⁷ TTe:1:319/148 (TT:1:11)

⁶⁸ TT:1:18, TTe1:185/17 and TT:2:149, TTe:5:412/1068.

history differently. His appreciation of Persian history for its completeness and reliable chronology could therefore have been independent of his assessment of the Persian era and thus explain why an era is missing in this part despite Ṭabarī's enthusiasm for Persian history.

3.5 Chronology Family tree

Just like in the text, we can see a chronology appear in the family tree. Individuals of the same generation have been placed at the same height in the family tree as much as possible. In this way, it becomes clear who lived approximately in the same generation. However, it is questionable to what extent the chronology of the family tree matches the chronology presented in the text.

In general, when comparing the chronology that Ṭabarī presents in *Tārīkh* with the family tree, we see that many individuals in the family tree did indeed live in the same generation according to the text. However, in several places, this is clearly not the case: sometimes individuals who are at the same height in the family tree are centuries apart in time according to the text. For example, ʿAmr (460f), king of the Lakhmids in al-Hira in the 3rd/4th century CE, is at the same height in the family tree as the prophet Sulaymān (466), who lived well before the Babylonian exile (6th century BCE).⁶⁹ It also occurs the other way around: some individuals who lived at the same time according to the text are in completely different generations in the family tree. For example, Bukht Naṣṣr (397), better known in English as the Babylonian king Nebuchadnezzar II, is much higher than Ṣadīqa (518), a king in Israel, while it is described that they both lived at the time of the Babylonian exile (6th century BCE).⁷⁰

When looking at the family tree from a distance, it is especially noticeable that one part of the family tree does not correspond chronologically to the rest of the family tree. This concerns the right part of the family tree (see blue-circled part in Figure 11). In Figure 11 several individuals who lived at the same time, according to the chronology in the text, are connected by a line. The green line connects the prophet Sulaymān (466) with Queen Yalmaḡah (252) who both lived well before the Babylonian captivity (6th century BC). The purple line connects the Lakhmid king ʿAmr

⁶⁹ The events described around both persons are 97 pages, or 204 of the English translation, separated from each other. (ʿAmr (460f): TT:1:408, TTe:4:150/771; Sulaymān (466): TT:1:311, TTe:3:147/567)

⁷⁰ TT:1:346, TTe:4:41/649.

(460f) with Muḥammad's ancestor Fihr (748) both of whom lived approximately in the 3rd/4th century CE. The red line connects the Abyssinian king in Yemen Abraha Al-Ashram (264c) with Muḥammad's grandfather 'Abd Al-Muṭṭalib (911) who, according to the text, negotiated with each other in the Year of the Elephant (circa 570 CE).

Figure 11. Overview of chronology in family tree.

Figure 12. Overview of chronology in family tree with alternative genealogy.

In Figure 11 we see that the orange Tribe of Lakhm (212), the light blue Tribe of Azd (249b), the dark blue Tribe of Qaḏā'a (315e), and the dark purple Tribe of Ṣayfī (173) (the lineages that are circled with blue), are 'higher' than their contemporaries on the left. This means that according to the chronology of the family tree, they lived in an

earlier generation than their contemporaries on the left side of the family tree. Figure 13 is a zoomed-in image of the top left of the blue square of Figure 11. It represents the part that connects the right and left sides of the family tree. Specific of interest is the part that is circled in green since this is the exact part that connects the right and left parts of the genealogy. The genealogy that we see in the green circle is based on the

Figure 13. Beginning lineage right side of family tree (upper part blue area Figure 11)

information Ṭabarī provides when he presents the lineages between Sām (64) in Ib-rāhīm (220). In Figure 13 however, we can see next to Saba' (152) that there is also an alternative genealogy available for this part. This alternative genealogy is introduced much later when Ṭabarī discusses the 2nd/3rd/4th century CE Kingdom of Lakhm. This alternative lineage is much longer than the one incorporated in the family tree: instead of three generations, the alternative lineage is twenty generations long. If this longer lineage were to be applied, the entire right part of the family tree would be moved further down. Figure 12 shows what the family tree would look like if the alternative lineage was used.

In Figure 12 the same lines are shown as in Figure 11. We see that applying the alternative genealogy causes the chronology of the family tree to be more in line with the chronology of the text, although there remains a large disparity between the purple and red lines. Nevertheless, the late introduction of this alternative genealogy is very interesting because it may indicate that Ṭabarī himself, or one of his sources, was aware that the right side of the lineage was much shorter than the left.⁷¹ From this perspective, the alternative genealogy can therefore be seen as a possible 'correction' to the family tree. The timing of the correction seems to support this theory as the alternative lineage comes up when discussing the lineage of the Lakhmids, a tribe that is part of the right side of the genealogy.⁷² The Lakhmids lived at the time of the early ancestors of Muḥammad, but that would not be possible from a genealogical perspective if the 'original' genealogy is maintained and thus an 'alternative' one may have been introduced.

3.6 Theory & Conclusion

In this chapter, *Tārīkh* and the family tree have been studied through the lens of time. The findings of the time analysis are all pieces of the puzzle in Ṭabarī's handling of time in his work of history. Below, these findings will be combined into a theory that attempts to explain Ṭabarī's handling of time in *Tārīkh*.

To begin, Ṭabarī does not use an era in the time period between Ādam and Muḥammad in *Tārīkh*. He only puts the events in chronological order. To make this possible, he decided to choose the Persian (king) history as a framework. He uses

⁷¹ Of course 'right' and 'left' are arbitrary in this case, but I'm referring here specifically to the way I have visualised it.

⁷² See in the family tree 'Tribe of Lakhm', the orange branch at the top right.

this history to chronologically organize the events of the histories he discusses. According to him, the king's history of the Persians is best suited as a framework because this history is the most complete and continuous. Given his appreciation of Persian history, it is striking that Ṭabarī does not use the Persian era, which is attached to the history, in this part of his work. This may indicate that Ṭabarī made a distinction between a reliable chronology and a reliable era: the Persian history qualifying for the first but not the latter. It is also possible that Ṭabarī was simply uncertain about the exact distribution of time in history and therefore refrained from giving an era in this part.

That time has an important place in the work of Ṭabarī is already evident from the introduction. Here Ṭabarī gives a comprehensive exposition of his concept of time. One of the points he addresses is the length of time. His conclusion, that 6500 years passed between Ādam and Muḥammad, attracted our attention because this conclusion tells us how many years elapsed in the first part of *Tārīkh*. However, unfortunately, Ṭabarī does not elaborate these 6500 years into time periods, making it difficult to get a concrete idea of the time structure of history. Also later on in the work, Ṭabarī does not return to these 6500 years at any point. This may have been because Ṭabarī's claim about the length of time is a theological and not a historic one. Ṭabarī probably simply could not find a historical source to support his claim which he based on traditions of the Prophet Muḥammad. The adoption of this claim in historiography could therefore be unusual within this research tradition. Also, the non-use of this claim, as with the non-use of the Persian era, could come from a possible uncertainty about the exact time distribution in history.

If we look at the family tree, we see that the chronology Ṭabarī presents in *Tārīkh* is largely reflected in the family tree. Genealogy thus seems to be supporting the chronology of historiography. However, it is the inconsistencies that attract our attention. Some individuals who were of the same generation according to the family tree, lived in completely different times according to the text. It also occurs the other way around: individuals who were contemporaries according to the text, lived in completely different times according to the family tree. Ṭabarī, or his sources, may have been partly aware of this mismatch between chronology and genealogy. This is reflected in the lineage of the Lakhmids as described in section 3.5. In this case, hundreds of pages after the initial lineage was described, a new lineage was introduced

which ensured that the genealogy of the Lakhmids was better aligned with the chronology in *Tārīkh*.

The new lineage of the Lakhmids also stood out because it contained many more generations than the previous ones and because these 'new' persons were not mentioned anywhere before. It is however not possible to determine whether this new lineage is a 'correction' to the aforementioned lineage, because that cannot be determined based on *Tārīkh* alone. Moreover, it is questionable whether the genealogical information in an elaborate form, such as a family tree, existed in Ṭabarī's time and if thus anyone could have noticed that a longer lineage made more sense. Nevertheless, the relative consistency between the chronology described and the family tree in combination with this 'correction' gives reason to think that there was some awareness among Ṭabarī, or his sources, about the relationship between chronology and genealogy. This is important because it shows the previously described development of the merging of genealogy and history discipline, in which genealogy became embedded in history over time because there was a need for context on the persons in the lineage,⁷³ thus possibly also meant that the disciplines had to agree to some extent. However, to establish such an assimilation process, much more research is needed.

Another way to look at the 'corrections' is from a functional point of view. What the 'corrections' do in the family tree is create a certain temporal distance between certain parts. This is reflected in Figures 11 and 12 where the lineage between Saba' (152) and Ya'rub (125) went from 3 to 20 generations. This meant that Saba's ancestor (152), Ya'rub (125), became more distant from his lineage in generational and temporal terms. This function may also be reflected in another phenomenon in the family tree: the extremely high ages of the persons between Ādam and Mūsā. Ṭabarī mentions that these individuals could reach a very old age, but it is not explained why. In any case, the advanced ages ensure that hundreds of years can be bridged in just a few generations. This causes the temporal distance between Ādam and Mūsā, and eventually, Ādam and Muḥammad, to become very large. The purpose of this was possibly to place the beginning of humanity in a distant and inaccessible past. This suggests that time in the historical descriptions of *Tārīkh* may not only be a factual representation but possibly simply an expression of temporal distances.

⁷³ See introduction, p. 5.

Finally, it is noticeable that in the family tree, some lineages are unequal: a split lineage comes together again while one split contains many more generations than the other. In paragraph 3.3 these unequal lineages were explained by the possibility of one side of the split having children later in life than the other split, a confusion of the words 'descendant/sons', 'son' and 'daughter' when copying the text or by forgetting or omitting ancestors who were considered unimportant. In any case, the fact that so many unequal lineages emerge in the family tree calls into question the earlier hypothesis that Ṭabarī, or his sources, possessed the family tree in an elaborate form and made "corrections" based on it. So the question remains to what extent this consciousness was really there and if it was there, how these unequal lineages were looked at. In *Tārīkh*, Ṭabarī himself pays no attention to the unequal lineages or inconsistencies in the chronology that emerges in the elaboration of the genealogical structure.

4 Findings & Analysis Site

Another angle from which to approach the family tree is through the element 'space'. Like time, space is a primary concern for historians. The events they describe always take place at a certain (geographical) location but we often also encounter the element of space through groups of people that claim certain (geographical) areas as their own or through the identity of a person that is linked to a specific area, city, or country. In *Tārīkh*, space is illuminated in all these ways. Often, Ṭabarī, or his sources, mentions the location where the events take place and which cities or towns are involved. In fact, mentioning the territories of kings is one of the objectives of the work, as Ṭabarī himself describes in the introduction:

[We intend to present] the dates of past kings mentioned by us and summaries of their history, the times of the messengers and prophets and how long they lived, the days of the early caliphs and some of their biographical data, and the extent of the territories under their control (*Mubālaghat walāyātihim*), as well as the events that took place in their age.⁷⁴

In addition to mentioning places and territories, space also returns in *Tārīkh* in the guise of tribes and folks. People who have a specific genealogy or have certain (physical) characteristics are often classified in *Tārīkh* under a collective name and given an 'original' living area as will be demonstrated below. Given the continued existence of these locations and folks/tribes into Ṭabarī's time, the manner in which Ṭabarī connects genealogy with space may provide more insight into the function of genealogy in his own time.

4.1 Tax & *Tārīkh*

As mentioned, space plays an important role in *Tārīkh*. Its interest in space might have something to do with land tax as place and its history are strongly linked to land tax. To explore this relationship I will first explain below how space and land tax relate to each other. Then I'll delve into what role land tax plays in *Tārīkh* and why it is an important topic, and lastly, I'll show how the relationship between space and land tax is reflected in the family tree.

⁷⁴ *Mubālaghat walāyātihim*, 'the range of their dominion,' can refer to both the range in time and in area as Rosenthal also points out in footnote 19. His translation 'the extent of the territories under their control' is very understandable since Ṭabarī regularly indicates over which territories a king rules. TTe:1:169/6. Between (...) own edit.

To better understand the relationship between space and land tax in Ṭabarī's context, it is best to look at his own works. Ṭabarī, born into a family of large land-owners⁷⁵, seems to have busied himself with land tax quite often. In his works, tax returns in different ways⁷⁶, but the most concrete example is the only remaining *fatwa*⁷⁷ we have of Ṭabarī. The *fatwa* can be found at the end of his *Musnad 'Alī* and appears to be directed at the Abbasid elite who were in power in the Islamic empire at the time. Ṭabarī advises in his *fatwa* about the payment of land tax. He makes a distinction between certain types of land and determines that different amounts of taxes must be paid for them. The two most important factors in determining what kind of land a particular area belongs to are its fertility and the way in which the area was conquered at the time of the expansion of the Islamic empire. The second factor is particularly interesting for this study as it involves history. It meant that if a territory had been conquered through battle, different tax rules applied than if there had been no fighting or the conquest took place by treaty. It was also important whether the inhabitants were Christian, Jewish, or pagan before the conquest and whether they became Muslim after the conquest.⁷⁸

Both the manner of conquest and the description of the religion and customs in a certain area are subjects that are fit to be recorded through history. When we look at *Tārīkh*, we see these topics return: Ṭabarī describes in the first part which territories belonged to which kings and what folks lived in them, and later, in the part after the death of the Prophet Muḥammad, he pays attention to how these territories were conquered.⁷⁹ These are exactly the data that Ṭabarī believes are important in determining the land tax. The genealogy and descriptions in *Tārīkh* may thus not only be of historical interest, but it might also be an expression of Ṭabarī's own idea, or an expression of a consensus, on the history of lands with its implication for how to tax it

⁷⁵ Rosenthal, *General introduction*, 13-14.

⁷⁶ According to Mårtensson, one of the debates that emerges in Ṭabarī's works is the discussion about who collect taxes: the central or local authority? And what are the rights and obligations of the local and central authority vis-à-vis each other? Mårtensson, *Madhhab Jarīrī*, 111-119.

An example of a work where Ṭabarī discusses taxation is the *Kitāb to the-Jizya*, 'The Book on Taxation', in his legal work *Ikhtilāf to the-Fuqahā'*. Joseph Schacht, *Das Konstantinopler Fragment des Ikhtilāf al-Fuqahā' des Abū Ja'far Muḥammad ibn Jarīr al-Ṭabarī* (Leiden: Brill, 1933), 2-199.

⁷⁷ A *fatwa* is a legal opinion of a scholar who is knowledgeable about the Islamic religious scriptures on an issue that is submitted to him/her. These issues are often about scenarios that are not clearly described in the sources and thus need to be looked at by a scholar who can employ different techniques to produce an answer.

⁷⁸ Ṭabarī, *Tahdhīb to the-Athār: Musnad 'Alī ibn Abī Ṭālib*, edited by Maḥmūd Muḥammad Shākir (Cairo: Al-Mu'assasa al-Sa'ūdiyya bi-Miṣr 1982), 289-291.

⁷⁹ See volume 3-4 of the Arabic text and 10-15 of the English translation.

in current times. This does not mean that *Tārīkh* was or could be used as a source by Ṭabarī or others to determine land tax, I have not found any example yet of this being the case, but indirectly *Tārīkh* does offer the opportunity for Ṭabarī to express his view on this matter.

To conclude, considering the attention that Ṭabarī pays to land tax in *Tārīkh*⁸⁰ and the connection between history and taxation, it is plausible that the treatment of space in history has a legal background.

4.2 Tax in the Family Tree

The previous section describes the relationship between tax and space and how this relates to history and more specifically *Tārīkh*. In this section, we investigate whether this relationship is also present in the family tree. If we were to adopt the hypothesis proposed in 4.1, it could mean that the places of individuals in the family tree are mainly within the borders of the current Abbasid empire. Figure 15 shows a map of the Middle East and its surrounding areas. On the map, the areas that belonged to a certain sphere of influence are indicated with a color. Figure 14 then uses the same color to encircle the groups of individuals who fall into these areas of influence. It is important to stress here though that the encirclement of individuals in Figure 14 does not mean that these persons lived in these specific empires, it simply means that the area where they used to live was part of a certain empire at the time of Ṭabarī.

⁸⁰ Ṭabarī, for instance, gives a lot of information about the state of affairs regarding the land tax under the rule of certain kings. For example: Manūshihir (TT:1:247-48, TTe:3:25-28/436-40), Zāw (TT:1:292, TTe:3:114-15/532) in Kisrā Anūsharwān: (TT:2:96-97, TTe:5:255-261/960-963).

Figure 14. Overview of family tree with encirclement of peoples who come from the same area. As the green box is very large, I have added the names of the areas where these people generally lived. The colors in Figures 14 and 15 correspond to each other.

Figure 15. Map Middle East and North Africa at the time of Ṭabari [225-310/840-922]. Legend: Yellow: Ifriqiyya and al-Andalus. Purple: Abyssinia. Green: Abbasid Empire. Red: Eastern Roman Empire. Blue: India. Grey: Rest of Africa. Egypt and Eastern Anatolia regularly changed spheres of influence. The map is only used to illustrate a point and is a simplified representation of reality. Blank map: Wikimedia Commons: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:BlankMap-World.svg#/media/File:BlankMap-World.svg>. (Colors are their own editing.)

Figures 14 and 15 show that, in accordance with the hypothesis, the family tree mainly contains individuals who, according to the text, resided in areas that later

belonged to the sphere of influence of the Abbasid central authority. As we can see in the family tree, the pedigree of individuals from non-Abbasid areas like those from sub-Saharan Africa, the Roman and Greek empires, and North Africa is at best only a few generations long. Thus, the genealogical information that Ṭabarī presents in *Tārīkh* indeed mainly focuses on the Abbasid areas. This supports the aforementioned hypothesis but is not yet confirmation this focus had anything to do with taxation. The focus could also be explained simply by the fact that Ṭabarī lived at the court of the Abbasid Empire and thus mainly had information about the Abbasid territories. The hypothesis thus remains an explorative one and further testing is needed to draw any conclusions about its plausibility.

4.3 People

Another way space is treated in *Tārīkh* is by referring to folks or tribes. When talking about a certain group of people, a specific area is often associated with it. This also applies to Ṭabarī and his sources, as we can see in *Tārīkh*. For example, in several places in the text, the area of a kingdom is referred to by referring to a people, such as "the king of the Turks," "a high-ranking person of Quraysh," or "the kingdom of the Persians."⁸¹ Although there is no direct reference to a specific space, a certain territory is meant by these descriptions since the area where (the majority of) these people are located is also the area over which the leader has or claims power.

In *Tārīkh* it is not entirely clear exactly how many folks there are or what a folk constitutes in the eyes of Ṭabarī. In any case, we first see folks appear when the sons of Nūḥ are discussed. According to Ṭabarī's sources, from the three sons of Nūḥ, Sām (64), Yāfath (68), and Ḥām (70), all kinds of peoples arose who moved to specific places in the world. Although the sources often give conflicting information, it becomes clear from these stories that humanity consists of all kinds of folks and that these have come to live in certain places.⁸² The way folks are described in this part gives reason to think that a description such as "the kingdom of the Persians" could also refer to a certain geographical area where "the Persian people" have settled

⁸¹ *Malak al-Turk* (TT:2:48, TTe:5:94), *sayyid Quraysh* (TT:2:85, TTe:5:224/938), *mamlakat ahl Fars* (TT:1:291, TTe:3:112/529)

⁸² The traditions about the exact classification are contradictory and inconclusive, but broadly speaking the classification is as follows: the sons of Ḥām lived in West and Sub-Saharan Africa, the sons of Sām in Middle East and around the Eastern-Mediterranean and Yāfath in Northern Europe and Central/East-Asia. See:TT:1:131-137, TTe:2:9-21/210-223.

"originally" instead of the area where Persians happen to live at that time. Anyway, there is a clear connection to be found between peoples and space in *Tārīkh*.

4.4 Arabs

The previous section briefly discussed the relationship between folks and geographical areas. In this section we will take a closer look at a specific people, namely the Arabs, to gain a better understanding of the relationship between people, genealogy, space, and *Tārīkh*.

In the introduction to this thesis, it was briefly mentioned that descent played an important role in social and religious matters in early Islamic times. To clarify this point, the *dīwān* system of the second caliph 'Umar was highlighted.⁸³ Individuals could enter this system if they belonged to the tribe of the Prophet or belonged to his early followers. When they were allowed into the system, they were entitled to a specific allowance. This privilege was inheritable and thus could also be passed on to further generations. As a result, the system was closely linked to genealogy and completely dominated people who lived in the Hijaz region at the time of Muhammad. Also later on, when the Islamic empire reached its greatest extent and further institutionalization took place, lineage remained important in several ways. During the Umayyad dynasty [41-132 / 661-750], many important government positions were held by Arabs from the 'Umayya clan, which was part of the tribe of the Prophet Muḥammad. In addition, non-Arabs were often completely excluded from elite positions and it was more difficult for non-Arabs to become Muslim.⁸⁴ Also after the Umayyad dynasty, when the Abbasids took power, the privileged position of Arabs and specific lineages was maintained for a long time.⁸⁵ This means that genealogy was still important politically and socially during Ṭabarī's lifetime. It is therefore interesting to investigate how this group, the Arabs, is represented in the family tree.⁸⁶

⁸³ See p. 5-6.

⁸⁴ G.R. Hawting, 'Umayyads,' in *Encyclopaedia of Islam Second Edition*, edited by P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs, et al., published 2000, accessed online April 12, 2023. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_1287.

⁸⁵ For a discussion of the privileged position of Arabs under Abbasids, see: B. Lewis, 'Abbāsids,' in *Encyclopaedia of Islam Second Edition*, edited by P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs, et al., published 1960, accessed online April 12, 2023. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_0002.

The importance of descent is also reflected in the name 'Abbasids'. This name is derived from their claim to be descendants of the Prophet's uncle, 'Abbās.

⁸⁶ According to Franz Rosenthal, Ṭabarī himself also suffered from the privileged position of Arabs. Although Ṭabarī probably came from an Arab family that had emigrated to Tabaristan, Ṭabarī's

In the family tree, there are several groups of Arabs. The first time the Arabs are mentioned in *Tārīkh* is in relation to the descendants of Lāwdh (79). He is presented as the ancestor of the so-called ‘*Āriba* Arabs. Ṭabarī explains that the ‘*Āriba* Arabs are the original Arabs who first spoke Arabic. Immediately upon introducing the ‘*Āriba* Arabs, Ṭabarī tells us that there is another group of Arabs, the *Muta‘arribah* Arabs. They are the descendants of Ismā‘īl (289), to whom the prophet Muhammad belongs, and they are ‘Arabisized’ Arabs, meaning they learned the Arabic language from those who already knew Arabic.⁸⁷ Lastly, we encounter a third group of Arabs later in the text: the descendants of Ya‘rub (125). Ṭabarī tells us little about why these descendants are Arabs but their identity can be derived from the fact that the name ‘Ya‘rub’ has the same consonants in Arabic as ‘Arab’ (ع - ر - ب). Also, later in *Tārīkh*, his descendants are referred to as Arabs.⁸⁸ In Figure 16 below, I have identified these three different groups in the genealogy.

intellectual opponents cast doubt on his origins, suggesting he might be (half) Persian. A non-Arab origin would imply, in the eyes of his opponents, that Ṭabarī’s view had less (theological) authority. Rosenthal *General Introduction*, 12-13.

⁸⁷ TT:1:133, TTe:2:13-14/215.

⁸⁸ See for example TT:1:397, TTe:4:128-129/745-746.

In Figure 16 we see reflected more clearly that the lineages of the different Arab groups emerge in different places. From a genealogical perspective, it is therefore not immediately clear why these three groups are all considered as ‘Arabs’: they lack a genealogical common ancestor, and the different ancestors, nor the first generations after, intermarry with the other Arab groups. In addition, their first common ancestor, which is Sam, is also the ancestor of non-Arab groups such as the Israelites and Greeks.⁸⁹ The exclusive trait among the Arab groups thus seems to be based on something else than genealogy. To find their common trade it might be important to

⁸⁹ The Greeks are considered descent from ‘Ayš (334) (Esau in the Christian tradition), the son of Işhāq (290). They are indicated in the boxes with a dark blue background and a red border in the middle of the family tree.

remind ourselves that Ṭabarī mentions that the acquisition of the Arabic language is a distinguishing factor between the *ʿĀriba* and *Mutaʿarrabah* Arabs. If language acquisition is a distinguishing factor between groups of Arabs, it is perhaps Arabic language proficiency in itself that is a distinguishing factor between Arabs and non-Arabs. This would mean that the term "Arab" is rather a linguistic category instead of a genealogical one. This fits well with the development of Arab identity as described by Peter Webb in *Imagining the Arabs*. According to him, language was a distinguishing factor between Arabs and non-Arabs in early Islamic times while the genealogical, and thus more static, definition of Arabness is a later development:

‘As the Arabic language spread amongst urban Iraqis alongside their conversion to Islam, and as Arab genealogy became more coherently articulated, Arabness discourses took refuge within the increasingly tangible boundaries of kinship, and open-ended notions of linguistic Arabness gave way to the closed-ended models of defining Arabs by genealogy.’⁹⁰

This language-oriented and genealogical definition of Arabness may explain what we see in the family tree. After all, *Tārīkh* was written after the development that Webb describes had taken place. The linguistic definition of Arab may thus have been used by Ṭabarī, and his sources, to distinguish the Arabs from the non-Arabs. Thereafter the language development of Arabic was traced back to certain ancestors, namely Lāwdh, Ismāʿīl, and Yaʿrub, which in turn become the ancestors of a genealogical interpretation of Arabness. In this way, we may get a glimpse of the development of Arab identity in the material in *Tārīkh*.⁹¹

Returning to the previous paragraph, it might be relevant to look at what role space has in the Arab/non-Arab distinction and the distinction between Arab groups. When we look at the text, we read that the three groups of Arabs lived in adjacent areas. We read that the *ʿĀriba* Arabs settled in Egypt, Palestine, Jordan, Bahrain, Yemen, Oman, and partly in the Hijaz,⁹² the *Mutaʿarrabah* Arabs lived mainly in the

⁹⁰ Peter Webb, *Imagining the Arabs* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2016), 223.

⁹¹ Just before the deadline of the thesis, the work of Webb, *Imagining the Arabs*, was brought to my attention by my supervisor. In Webb’s book, among other things, the different Arabic groups and how they became genealogical conceptualized by early Muslims is discussed. This work deserved more attention here, but due to the circumstances only appears minimally in this thesis. See Disclaimer (p. 4)

⁹² Bahrain here refers to the region in the North of the Arabian Peninsula and not to the modern state of Bahrain.

Egypt: TT:1:134, TTe:2:16/217. Palestine: TT:1:301, TTe:3:129/548. Jordan, Syria, Bahrain, Yemen, Oman and partly in the Hijaz: TT:1:133 TTe:2:14/215.

Hijaz and later also in Southern Iraq⁹³, and the *Ya'rub* Arabs lived in Yemen and later also in Southern Iraq and Bahrain.⁹⁴ It is noticeable that there are minimal similarities between the habitats of the Arab groups which may signify that space is a distinguishing factor between the Arab groups. The relatively exclusive living area of the *Ya'rub* Arabs in Yemen for instance may have been a motivation to distinguish them from the other Arab groups. When it comes to the Arab/non-Arab distinction, space might also play a certain role. But as the areas where the Arabs lived were also inhabited by other non-Arab folks, it is difficult to see how space can be a distinguishing factor between Arabs and non-Arabs.

All in all, we can derive from the way the Arabs are described in the text that the Arab/non-Arab distinction may be linguistic rather than genealogical. The separation of the Arabs into three groups, the *ʿĀriba*, *Mutaʿarribah*, and *Ya'rub* Arabs, on the other hand, seems to be based on genealogy, geography, and language acquisition.

4.5 Muḥammad, The Last Prophet

Finally, we can also consider space, as in genealogical nearness, within the family tree itself. Namely, we see that the lineages of some tribes are more closely linked to each other through marriage than others. One interesting look at space in the genealogy is through the focus of Newby's book *The Making Of The Last Prophet* which was discussed in section 1.1. The central theory in this book was that the stories about earlier prophets in Ibn Ishāq's *Sīra* contained certain elements that would predict or confirm the prophethood of Muḥammad. As Newby was able to apply this theory with some success to the material he used, it might be interesting to see if this theory is also applicable to the genealogical information we find in Ṭabarī's work. In other words, here we will ask ourselves: how do earlier prophets in the family tree relate to Muḥammad?

⁹³ The primal ancestor of Muḥammad's lineage, Ismāʿīl, settled in Mecca. Given the fact that Muḥammad is still in Mecca, a continuous presence in the Hijaz is plausible. Ismāʿīl in Mecca TT:1:164-165, TTe:2:69-71/274-276. Southern Iraq: TT:1:397, TTe:4:128/745.

⁹⁴ Yemen, Southern Iraq and Bahrain: TT1:397, TTe:4:128-129/745-746.

When we look at the family tree, we see that most of the prophets are in the pink section of the Israelites. We also see that the lineage of ʿĪsā (605), in the Christian tradition Jesus, flows from the Israelite section. It is noticeable that the light purple lineage of the Prophet Muḥammad is not connected to these Israelite prophets in any way except for their first common ancestor Ibrāhīm (220). In Figure 17 we can see this part of the lineage. We see that the lineage of the Israelites starts with Ibrāhīm's son Iṣḥāq (290) and that Muḥammad's lineage starts with Ismāʿīl (289).

Figure 17. Split lineage at Ibrāhīm (220)

The split that occurs at Ibrāhīm (220) is exceptional; it is the only place in the family tree where the lineage seems to be determined by the mother rather than the father. Only the prophets from Ādam up until Ibrāhīm are thus part of the lineage of both Muḥammad and the Israelite prophets. In addition to a separation in the family tree, the separation of Ibrāhīm's two sons is also symbolized in *Tārīkh* by a separation in space: Ismāʿīl (289) is left with his mother in Mecca, and Iṣḥāq (290) stays with his father and mother in Syria.⁹⁵

This means that from the point of Ibrāhīm, there are virtually no prophets in the lineage of the prophet Muḥammad. Except for Ismāʿīl (289), not one of Muḥammad's ancestors is considered a prophet, while the Israelite lineage has about ten. The genealogical link with the prophets who preceded Muḥammad is thus very thin, but this does not mean that these lineages were far apart in the eyes of Islamic scholars. In *Tārīkh* we find a story in which the Israelite prophets concern themselves about the lineage of the prophet Muḥammad. This story occurs when Ṭabarī discusses the Babylonian exile. It describes how the Israelites during their exile tried to convince Bukht Naṣṣr (397), king of Babylon, to attack the Arabs. Bukht Naṣṣr (397) succumbs to the pressure from the Israelites and begins preparations for his attack. Then the story is interrupted and we read about two Israelite prophets, Irmīyyā (456) and Barkhiyyā (530), who are sent on a mission by God to the Arabian Peninsula. The reason for this assignment is that an Arab, Maʿadd (553), is about to be attacked by

⁹⁵ Ismāʿīl in Mecca: TT:1:164-165, TTe:2:70-71/276-77. Iṣḥāq in Syria: TT:175-176, TTe:2:89-90/300-301.

the army of Bukht Naṣṣr (397) and must be saved from death. Rescuing this person from the hands of Bukht Naṣṣr's army is very important, we are told, because from his descendants an important prophet will arise (i.e. Muḥammad). In the end, the Israelite prophets successfully completed the mission and thus preserved the Arab lineage.⁹⁶

So, although there is no genealogical link in the family tree between Muḥammad and most of the prophets mentioned in *Tārīkh*, the lineages of the prophets are connected by a story. The Israelite prophets emphatically protect Muḥammad's lineage and thus confirm the importance of his lineage. This shows that genealogical distance can be made less or more significant through narratives.

4.6 Theory & Conclusion

In this chapter, we studied *Tārīkh* and the family tree through the lens of space. We saw that naming the geographical location of the events in history is very important to Ṭabarī. This can be derived from the introduction to the work and the fact that there is almost always a geographical location mentioned when an event is described. The importance of space is also reflected in the family tree: it is possible to determine where they have lived of most individuals. In Figure 14, we were thus able to create an overview of the areas where the individuals lived. When we compared Figure 14 to a contemporary map of the Abbasid Empire during Ṭabarī's life, it became clear that the persons from the family tree lived mainly in the area that later belonged to the Abbasid Empire. The focus on this area is probably related to the fact that Ṭabarī lived at the court of the Abbasid Empire and therefore mainly had access to the history of this area. This focus was also linked to tax policy in Ṭabarī's time in sections 4.1 and 4.2. The purpose of making this connection was to suggest a possible administrative relevance of *Tārīkh* to Ṭabarī's present. The connection is only the beginning of a hypothesis and more research is needed to confirm this connection.

Another way of referring to space we see in *Tārīkh* is through tribes and folks. For example, the Sassanid Empire is referred to in one place as "the kingdom of the Persians." The way the concept of 'people' is used in the beginning of *Tārīkh* reflects the idea that certain ancestors and genealogies are linked to a certain habitat. This is reflected in the information about the descendants of the three sons of Nūḥ.

⁹⁶ TT:1:360-361, TTe:4:66-70/671-675.

According to the sources cited by Ṭabarī, the sons of Yāfath (68) became the folks of Europe and Central/East Asia, those of Ḥām (70) became the peoples of sub-Saharan and West Africa, and those of Sām (64) the folks the Middle East and the Eastern-Mediterranean. We then turned our attention to a specific people, the Arabs, to better our understanding of the relationship between folk, space, and genealogy. This study showed that perhaps genealogy is only part of how folks are constructed. The case of the Arabs showed that language may have been a very important initial factor in distinguishing between peoples. This ties in with the development of the concept of 'Arab' according to Peter Webb which we briefly discussed. The combination of a fluid linguistic definition and a more fixed genealogical (and geographical?) definition of Arab in *Tārīkh* shows the complexity of defining folks and tribes. Ultimately, we can derive from the fact that in *Tārīkh* tribes and folks are carefully constructed in history through genealogy that possibly genealogy has a legitimizing role in the use of folks/tribes as (static) actors in history.

Finally, we saw that genealogical, and geographical, distance does not necessarily entail that lineages are far apart in the way they can be interpreted. This was reflected in the lineages of Muḥammad and the Israelite prophets. Geographically we saw that, from Ismāʿīl (289) onward, Muḥammad's ancestors settled in Mecca while the Israelite people settled in Palestine. Genealogically there was also a great distance between the two lineages as no marriages are mentioned between the two lineages from Ibrāhīm onward. Yet the two lineages are meaningfully connected through a story of two Israelite prophets who are sent on a mission by God to save an ancestor of Muḥammad. They are given this assignment because an important prophet will rise from this ancestor. Carrying out this command implies that the Israelite prophets recognize the prophethood of Muḥammad and care for his lineage. Thus, despite the geographical and genealogical distance between the two lineages, the lineages are connected through prophethood and narrative.

5 Conclusion

In this thesis, I examined the genealogical information in the first part of the work *Tārīkh al-Rusul wa-l-Mulūk* by Abū Ja‘far Muḥammad ibn Jarīr al-Ṭabarī. In the introduction, I have delineated the first part of *Tārīkh* to the period from the first man Ādam to the prophet Muḥammad. The Persian genealogical information mentioned in this part was excluded from this research due to the time and space limitations I had for my thesis. The research question to which this thesis provides an answer is: *What was the function of the genealogical information, mentioned in the period from Ādam to Muḥammad, in the historical work Tārīkh al-Rusul wa-l-Mulūk within the text itself and for its author, Ṭabarī?*

To investigate the function of the genealogical information, the textual information from the first part of *Tārīkh* was visualized in the form of a family tree. The visualization shows that most lineages generally fit well together and that they show a large degree of coherence. The impressive consistency in the nearly 1300-name family tree is very striking given that the lineages originate from a dozen different sources and are very far apart in the text. The consistency suggests that the genealogical information was carefully compiled, either by Ṭabarī himself or perhaps some earlier consensus-making, and that it must have been considered important in Ṭabarī's time that the genealogical information showed coherence. In addition, the fact that so much attention is paid to genealogy in this work indicates that it was considered a valuable part of history.

When we look into the function of the genealogical information within *Tārīkh* itself, we can see a significant connection between genealogy and historiography. In the analysis of the family tree through the lens of time, there was a decent consistency between the chronology of the genealogy and history. It even seems that 'corrections' are being made to the lineages to make it more chronologically in line with the historiography. The genealogical information thus seems to play a supporting and affirming role with regard to the chronology in the historiography of *Tārīkh*. However, the inconsistencies that occur in the chronology between the genealogy and historiography and the inclusion of unequal lineages in the genealogy both show that there was no complete assimilation between the two sciences in *Tārīkh*. In the analysis of genealogy through the lens of space, we have also distinguished that genealogy also has a legitimizing function in historiography. This we saw through our study

of the subdivision of the people into folks and tribes. Although "folk" or "tribe" does not have a fixed definition in Ṭabarī's work, there is a strong connection between these terms and genealogy, space, and language in the way they are used. The embedding of folks and tribes in genealogy and assigning them a genealogical starting point gives Ṭabarī, and his sources, the opportunity to use these peoples as actors throughout history. Genealogy thus seems to support and legitimize the use of folks and tribes as actors in *Tārīkh*.

As for the function of the genealogical information in *Tārīkh* for Ṭabarī's time, there are two main findings. Expanding upon the last point in the previous paragraph, we see that the subdivision of persons into "folks" and "tribes" in the genealogy legitimizes the existence of these peoples as actors in history. An interesting people to look at in this regard are the Arabs since they enjoyed a privileged position in early Islamic times in the Islamic empires. The subdivision in the genealogy of the Arabs into three different groups prompted the idea that perhaps this reflected a way of differentiating between Arabs themselves and thereby excluding some Arab groups from the privileged position in favor of other Arabs. To draw this conclusion, however, more research is needed. Moving on, the genealogy might also be considered as an expression of Ṭabarī's, or his peers', view on the taxability of land. As a jurist, Ṭabarī was involved in land taxation as evidenced by, among others, the only remaining *fatwa* we have from him. This *fatwa* shows that the history of an area and the history of its people, and thus also possibly its genealogy, were important factors in determining the type of land tax to should be paid. Although *Tārīkh* itself is not a source for determining the tax, it may express a certain view on the taxability of land.

All in all, it follows from this research that the genealogical information in *Tārīkh* plays a supporting and legitimizing role in historiography by creating coherence between persons through folks and tribes and by its agreement with the chronology of the historiography itself. As for the function of genealogical information for Ṭabarī, we see that genealogy is primarily a reflection of how he, and probably others in his time, understood history and the contemporary world around him. Genealogy can be seen here as playing a legitimizing role: the use of peoples as actors in history and Ṭabarī's time is justified by the placing of their genealogy in history.

5.1 Reflection And Follow-Up Research

In this study, the genealogical information in *Tārīkh* was examined based on a family tree. The choice for this approach was already explained in the introduction. However, it is important to mention that the family tree is, of course, only a construct: it is not clear whether Ṭabarī himself considers the genealogical information in *Tārīkh* suitable for creating a family tree or if he imagines the genealogy like this at all. Organizing this information into a family tree has important consequences for the way in which the information is perceived. It creates an overview of the lineages that is not immediately apparent in the text, masks the different ideas about lineage that Ṭabarī presents by including only one lineage (and placing the other lineages elsewhere), and may sometimes give a distorted or incomplete picture of Ṭabarī's view of tribal affiliations of individuals by using colors. Despite this, the family tree does present us with a lot of valuable insights into the structure of the genealogical information which was previously not exactly known. Therefore, The family tree is thus a useful tool to examine the genealogical information but by no means a replacement for the text.

A shortcoming of the current family tree is that it is impossible to derive from it what influence Ṭabarī himself had on the material and what influence his informants exercised. The family tree does not show which lineages come from which source(s). It is therefore questionable to what extent the sources themselves already base themselves on a coherent genealogy and what influence Ṭabarī has had on creating a more/less consistent whole. For the conclusions in this thesis and our understanding of the family tree, it is thus really important to take into account that Ṭabarī is not the only person who has influenced the genealogy. For follow-up research, it would be very interesting to add the sources for each lineage to the family tree. Only then we will be able to see how Ṭabarī uses his sources for different parts of the genealogy and the influence he had himself on the genealogical information. Moreover, it will also provide insight into how he deals with his Christian and Jewish sources which he paraphrases often.

Furthermore, the inclusion of the Persian genealogical information that Ṭabarī mentions in the period between Ādam to Muḥammad in the family tree would be very valuable. The inclusion of this material offers a variety of options for follow-up research. For example, the Persian family tree can be used as comparison material to the findings from the Arab and Israelite family trees. In addition, a comparison of the Persian, Arab, and Israelite family trees can give us more insight into exactly how

Ṭabarī tries to connect these different histories. The inclusion may also contribute to the study of Persian/Zoroastrian influences on the understanding of (the history of) Islam for Muslims in early Islamic times. The elaboration of Persian genealogical information would thus contribute to the understanding of the complex coherence of the Persian, Arab, and Islamic experiences which, as briefly discussed in section 1.3, was/is the basis of the understanding of Islam for many Muslims throughout history.

The results of this research also provide an opportunity to further delve into the administrative relevance of *Tārīkh* to Ṭabarī's own time. Apart from Mårtensson's work, few other attempts have been made to investigate the administrative relevance of the work. This is striking since *Tārīkh's* relevance might also be in guiding everyday governance or expressing views on administrative issues. The connection made in this thesis between *Tārīkh*, genealogy, and taxation is only one of the many possibilities to explain the relevance of *Tārīkh*. Also, studying the use of the term "Arab" in this work, as presented in paragraph 4.4, might provide a gateway to examine *Tārīkh's* relevance for Ṭabarī's present. The work of Webb could serve as interesting comparative material for this.

Finally, the family tree presented in this study can also more generally be used by other researchers as reference material. The complete family tree and the register will therefore also be published in due course. This will allow researchers to more easily familiarize themselves with the complex structure of this part of *Tārīkh* and to be able to use it for their own analyses.

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Appendix A

Other uploads within this project

Visualisation of Genealogy: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10066053>

Register Genealogy: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10066103>